

D5.1

Report on the Framework Integration and Demonstrator Status (M26)

PSNC

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Abstract

This document is a report on the status of the work package 5 activities regarding the set-up and maintenance of the continuous integration tools and processes that support and guide the integration and release of the DATAMITE framework. Furthermore, it covers the activities related to the six project use case demonstrators' developments, integration and testing as well

as training material development.

Keywords

Framework, demonstrator, integration, pilots, tests, pipeline, training, feedback

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Nature of the deliverable

R*

Dissemination level

PU Public, fully open. e.g., website

✓

CL Classified information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

SEN Confidential to DATAMITE project and Commission Services

* Deliverable types:

R: document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).

DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.

DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMI	Advanced Metering Infrastructure
API	Application Programming Interface
CAPEX	CAPital EXpenditure
CD	Continuous Delivery
CDO	Chief Data (Strategy) Officer
CI	Continuous Integration
CRM	Customer Relationship Management
DER	Distributed Energy Resource
DIHs	Digital Innovation Hubs
DPO	Data Protection Officer
DSLAM	Digital Subscriber Line Access Multiplexer
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EC	European Commission
EDC	Eclipse Dataspace Components
EU	European Union
EV	Electric Vehicle
FTTH	Fiber-to-the-Home
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GUI	Graphical User Interface
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
IT	Information Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MDM	Meter Data Management
OLAP	Online Analytical Processing
OLTP	Online Transaction Processing
OPEX	OPerating EXpense
PoC	Proof-of-Concept
RES	Renewable Energy Source
RTU	Remote Terminal Unit
SCADA	Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition

SQL	Structured Query Language
VDSL	Very high-speed Digital Subscriber Line
VM	Virtual Machine
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This document serves to provide a comprehensive overview of the current status and progress of the various tasks associated with Work Package 5, which focuses on the integration and deployment of system components. Adopting a structured CI/CD approach facilitated the integration process and laid the groundwork for the continued evolution of the DATAMITE framework. The work done on this matter is a joint effort of three parts: tools and technologies, CI/CD pipeline, and procedures.

The first version of the six Use Case Demonstrators has been developed and deployed to validate and refine the framework. They represent a bridge between innovative research and practical application, allowing WP5 to make the framework accessible to a wider community. By simulating realistic conditions, each Demonstrator provided insights into how DATAMITE can be operationalised across different contexts. In the course of test scenarios definition, training planning, and test campaigns, varied user interactions have been initiated, ultimately enhancing framework applicability and relevance. Each of the Pilots was an opportunity to perform activities grouped into:

- Test Scenarios
- Solution implementation
- Training materials planned
- Test Campaign
- Feedback for improving design
- Validation KPIs
- Performance and usability

In conclusion, the progress made in Work Package 5 demonstrates a concerted effort to integrate and deploy system components effectively, prepare delivery of impactful training, and conduct thorough testing. The work described in the document will be continued and presented in

deliverable D5.2 in month 36 with the final version of the Framework and use cases component descriptions.

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1. Introduction

DATAMITE is a project funded by the European Commission as part of the Horizon Europe programme and coordinated by the ITI - Technological Institute of Informatics. DATAMITE empowers European companies by delivering a modular, open-source and multi-domain Framework to improve DATA Monetising, Interoperability, Trading and Exchange, in the form of software modules, training, and business materials.

DATAMITE unleashes the monetisation potential at two levels. At internal level, users will have tools to improve quality management of their data, the adherence to FAIR principles, and will be able to upskill on technical and business aspects thanks to the multiple open-source training materials the project will generate. Therefore, data will become trustable and more reliable also in other paradigms like AI.

At external level, keeping users in control of their data will provide new sources of revenue and interaction with other stakeholders. The architecture envisioned for DATAMITE enables DIHs sandboxing, becoming a potential instructor on their onboarding of SMEs and low-tech SMEs into the data economy. Together, DATAMITE's solutions will function as a catalyst to boost data monetisation in the European productive fabric.

Work Package 5 (WP5), "Integration, Demonstration, and Validation," plays a critical role in the DATAMITE project by focusing on the seamless integration and release of the DATAMITE framework. This WP acts as the central hub for consolidating advancements from other technical work packages, ensuring compatibility and cohesion. To facilitate this process, WP5 is responsible for delivering and maintaining the necessary tools and procedures, including a robust repository and comprehensive CI/CD pipelines, enabling smooth integration and rigorous testing. Key to WP5's goals is the development and deployment of six use case demonstrators, built upon the DATAMITE framework. These demonstrators serve as a validation platform, showcasing the framework's potential and practicality in real-world and realistic settings. The results and insights derived from these demonstrations will be crucial for exploitation and dissemination efforts, while also providing invaluable evaluation and validation feedback to inform ongoing development tasks.

The core objectives of WP5 are: to continuously integrate the technical advancements from other work packages (O5.1); to prepare and validate Data Tech Training Materials within the context of

pilot programs (O5.2); and to prepare, deploy, demonstrate, validate, and evaluate the DATAMITE framework within these same pilot settings (O5.3).

1.1. Deliverable Purpose and Scope

Specifically, the Grant Agreement states the following regarding this Deliverable:

Report on status of the developments and releases of components' integration and pilots, training material and test campaign.

Hence, the purpose of this document is to outline the progress of the Work Package 5 tasks. These concern implementation and integration of components conducted within Task 5.1, advance in pilots' deployments (Task 5.2), training preparation activities carried out in Task 5.3 that provide valuable feedback on real-world usage and identify areas for optimisation through test campaigns (Task 5.4).

1.2. Document Structure

This deliverable is broken down into the following sections:

- **Executive Summary:** A summary of the contents and main findings are provided.
- **Section 1 Introduction** provides the deliverable's general context, dependencies, and structure.
- **Section 2 DATAMITE Framework Integration** carries out the essential CI/CD strategy for the DATAMITE framework, focusing on tools and processes to ensure all framework components are effectively integrated and deployed systematically. Further, we will explore the specific technologies, pipelines, and procedures mandatory for the DATAMITE CI/CD process.
- **Section 3 Trainings** describes the trainings and courses planning.
- **Section 4 Use Case Demonstrators** describes the deployment of beta solutions integrating the first iteration of created components. This part also involves the conduction of internal and external beta tests that contribute to the refinement and optimization of the next iteration.
- **Section 5 Conclusions** summarizes the work completed so far.

1.3. Document Dependencies

This document is the first iteration of the deliverable, which will also be delivered in M36. This deliverable provides the status regarding the Framework Integration and Demonstrator showing their progress throughout the project. This deliverable follows an initial analysis of the pilots that has been done in deliverable D1.1 (*Roadmap and pilots' definition*). The technical requirements coming from the pilots that influenced the architecture of the project have been captured in deliverable D1.2 (*Requirements and architecture*). The data management plans of the pilots have been described in the deliverables D7.7 and D7.8 (*Data Management Plan and Data Protection Plan*).

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2. DATAMITE Framework Integration

This section focuses on establishing and maintaining continuous integration and continuous deployment (CI/CD) tools and processes to ensure the seamless integration and systematic release of the DATAMITE framework. It covers the entire framework, ensuring that all components and tools are effectively integrated. The process adheres to well-defined procedures and an agreed-upon release plan, fostering consistency and reliability. By adopting this structured approach, a solid foundation is being established for a cohesive and efficient integration process, enabling the successful deployment and evolution of the DATAMITE framework. In greater detail, this section analyses and explains the mandatory tools and technologies, pipelines, and procedures defined for the CI/CD process to support the release of the DATAMITE framework.

2.1. Tools & technologies

2.1.1. GitLab Repository

GitLab serves as a source code repository where developers openly and collaboratively store, manage, and track changes to the codebase. It integrates CI/CD pipelines, called GitLab Runners, to automate testing, building, and deployment tasks. A centralised version control system is crucial for maintaining consistency, managing code changes, and automatically triggering CI/CD pipelines when new code is pushed. In the DATAMITE framework, the [GitLab repository](#).

This GitLab instance and the GitLab Runners are hosted by ECL and provided as part of the DATAMITE infrastructure. Other tools and templates, such as the *Eclipse Secretsmanager* or *BuildKit* and its templates (explained below as part of the DockerHub process) are provided as part of the ECL infrastructure for DATAMITE as well.

Finally, all the data related to GitLab and DATAMITE is stored in Europe.

2.1.2. DockerHub Account

DockerHub is a cloud-based registry for storing, sharing, and managing Docker images. Developers upload prebuilt container images to DockerHub for easy access during deployment. It provides a centralized platform for hosting container images used in CI/CD pipelines, enabling automated builds and ensuring consistent deployments across environments. In DATAMITE, a [DockerHub account](#) is used to manage the relevant Docker images.

CI builds include a template that consumes services such as BuildKit and Secretsmanager. While BuildKit is used to build Docker images, the Secretsmanager is a secrets store used to push Docker images to DockerHub.

2.1.3. Virtual Machine (VM)

A virtual machine simulates a physical computing environment and is used to host applications and services during the CI/CD process. VMs are used to create isolated and controlled environments for building, testing, and deploying applications, ensuring consistency across various stages of the pipeline. Moreover, The VM requires proper network configuration to ensure access to the internet and seamless communication between all CI/CD components.

2.1.4. Docker and Docker Swarm

Another dependency is that the VMs must have Docker installed. Docker is a platform that packages applications and their dependencies into containers, making them portable and consistent across environments. This results in a Docker Swarm deployment. Docker Swarm is Docker's native orchestration tool that allows clustering and management of multiple Docker nodes for running services at scale. Finally, the DATAMITE framework provides configuration details, and commands needed to deploy and manage the [infrastructure services](#). Figure 1 depicts DATAMITE's Docker Swarm architecture. Additionally, besides the Swarm implementation, DATAMITE also aims to deploy the framework on Kubernetes.

Figure 1: Docker Swarm Architecture

2.2. CI/CD Pipeline

2.2.1. Runners and stages

The CI/CD pipeline for the DATAMITE project leverages runners and defined stages to automate the development, testing, and deployment processes. Below is a detailed explanation of the configuration.

2.2.1.1. Runners in the DATAMITE Eclipse Repository

The runner pipelines are already enabled in the DATAMITE Eclipse repository. Runners act as agents that execute the CI/CD jobs defined in the pipeline, enabling automated builds, tests, and deployments.

2.2.1.2. Pipeline Stages

The pipeline consists of the following key stages:

Test (Optional): This stage is designed for testing purposes, allowing teams to validate code or configurations before proceeding to the next steps.

Build: During the build stage, the following operations are performed:

- A Docker image is built based on the project configuration.
- The pipeline authenticates to DockerHub.
- The built image is pushed to the DATAMITE DockerHub repository for centralized management.

Deploy/Notify: The deploy/notify stage involves deploying the application to the relevant infrastructure. The operations include:

- Pulling the Docker image from DockerHub.
- Deploying the image to the designated infrastructure, such as a virtual machine (VM).

2.2.2. CI/CD Procedure Flow

The CI/CD process for the DATAMITE project has been designed to streamline the building, deployment, and management of Docker images across the infrastructure. Below is a detailed description of the workflow:

- **Building the Docker Image**

The process begins with building a Docker image using Eclipse Runners. These runners execute the necessary steps to compile, package, and prepare the image for deployment.

- **Pushing the Docker Image to DockerHub**

Once the Docker image is built, it is pushed to DockerHub under the DATAMITE project's dedicated account. This centralized repository ensures that all project-related Docker images are accessible and consistently managed.

- **Triggering Operations via the DATAMITE Infrastructure Project**

Any project within the DATAMITE ecosystem that executes its CI/CD pipeline can trigger a job in the DATAMITE CI/CD infrastructure project. This project is responsible for performing all necessary operations on the client server, ensuring seamless integration and deployment.

- **Remote Operations on the Client Server**

The triggered job in the infrastructure project establishes an SSH connection with the remote virtual machine (VM). Through this connection, the following operations are executed:

1. Pulling the newly built Docker image from DockerHub.
2. Executing the required Docker commands to configure the image.

3. Restarting services to apply the updates and ensure the proper functioning of the system. This streamlined CI/CD procedure ensures efficient deployment and management of Docker images, promoting consistency and reducing manual intervention across the DATAMITE project's infrastructure, as Figure 2 depicts.

Figure 2: Pipeline

2.3. Procedures

To optimize the CI/CD pipeline and avoid unnecessary image builds, we have established a set of rules to configure the pipeline effectively. These rules ensure that jobs are triggered only when specific conditions are met, reducing overhead and streamlining processes. Below is an overview of the key rules.

2.3.1. Rules for Specific Branches

This rule ensures that jobs are triggered only when working with designated branches. For example, the following condition limits job execution to the main branch:

```
if: $CI_COMMIT_BRANCH == "main"
```

Similarly, the following one allows support for the develop branch with the condition:

```
if: $CI_COMMIT_BRANCH == "develop"
```

2.3.2. Trigger for Merge Requests

This rule retains the condition for merge request events, ensuring jobs are triggered whenever a merge request is created or updated:

```
if: $CI_PIPELINE_SOURCE == "merge_request_event"  
when: always
```

2.3.3. Tag-Specific Triggers

Jobs can also be triggered based on specific version tags. This is useful for creating version-specific builds:

```
if: $CI_COMMIT_TAG  
when: always
```

2.3.4. Environment-Specific Rules

Conditions can be added to trigger jobs for specific environments, such as `production`. This enables tailored actions for different deployment environments:

```
if: $CI_ENVIRONMENT_NAME == "production"  
when: always
```

2.3.5. Combining Conditions

For more precise control, combined logic can be used. For instance, the following condition triggers jobs only for merge requests targeting the main branch:

```
if: $CI_COMMIT_BRANCH == "main" && $CI_PIPELINE_SOURCE ==  
"merge_request_event" when: always
```

These rules enhance the CI/CD pipeline's efficiency by limiting job execution to relevant scenarios. By applying these conditions, we reduce unnecessary builds, streamline resource usage, and ensure the pipeline aligns with project requirements.

3. Trainings

This section describes the DATAMITE approach towards the preparation of the training materials and courses as part of the activities conducted under T5.3. This task, in collaboration with WP2, WP3, and WP4, is responsible for the preparation of the online training materials associated with modules from WP2 and WP3 that will conform the *DATA Tech training material*.

The goal of preparing the courses in DATAMITE is to:

- Promote services and tools
- Encourage best use of services and tools
- Gather feedback on services
- Increase user base and community
- Support achievement of the KPIs

This material will consider different target users: administrators to guide the deployment of the DATAMITE framework, users of the framework, e.g. use cases developers for best practices in integration with the framework, or end users of the use cases for the uptake and exploitation of the services.

The main part of this task will be performed in the last year of the project. Training will follow the guidance in the training development, using the *Creating quality online courses* guide and templates of the EOSC-Synergy project on training analysis and training design. Those guidelines have been introduced to the consortium partners responsible for content creation. The methodology takes as a pattern the well-known ADDIE (Analyse, Design, Develop, Implement) overarching framework, and is composed of the several stages including:

- Initial analysis of the training: Before starting to create training materials, it's essential to think about the motive for running the training and to consider the audience and learning outcomes. It is also a good idea to consider practical issues at this stage, such as timing and available resources. The template for initial training analysis has been provided and it includes areas to examine listed below:
 - Overall aim and training objective(s)
 - Audience and pre-requisites
 - Learning outcomes
 - Topics to cover
 - Delivery methods

- Timescale and resources required
- Design of the courses: From many methods one can follow, the ABC-Learning Design (ABD-LD) method developed by University College London will be used. This method introduces different learning activity types and operates through the storyboarding learner's journey. The template for the design has been provided. Training is to be performed in different forms using tools like Moodle for hosting necessary materials, such as podcasts or series of short videos complemented with the presentations. All the training materials will be validated.

The initial list of the courses, as well as the initial timeline, has been identified in Table 1.

Course name	Company name	Form of the course	Start date	Delivery date	Language
How to install and use the DATAMITE framework from the user's perspective	CERTH	Documentation, Live or recorded sessions	2025-02-01	2025-03-26	English
Data governance tools or data governance and quality tools	ITI	Series of short movies, Documentation	2025-02-01	2025-03-26	English
How to deploy and use DATAMITE framework: a step-by-step guide	OTE	Moodle course	2025-02-01	2025-03-28	English
Integration of the different modules of DATAMITE in infrastructures (cloud, local or "on-premises" deployment)	GIDITEK	Documentation, Live or recorded sessions	2025-03-20	2025-04-10	English, Spanish
Intro to Dataspace for Data Consumers	HEDNO	Series of short movies, Moodle course	2025-02-15	2025-04-30	English
Enhancing Mistral Visibility through DATAMITE	CINECA	Moodle course, Live webinar	2025-02-01	2025-08-10	English
Data provider integration with Pontus-X	PSNC	Series of short movies, Moodle course	2025-03-01	2025-04-28	English

Publication/User Instructions	1001 Lakes	Publication/User Instructions	2025-04-01	2025-04-28	English
Intro to Dataspaces for Data Providers	HEDNO	Moodle course	2025-03-15	2025-05-15	Greek
How to use CI/CD procedures in DATAMITE to commit the codes, from the developer's perspective	CERTH	Documentation, Live or recorded sessions	2025-03-26	2025-05-26	English
The open source side of DATAMITE (open source licenses and business models)	ECL	Live webinar which could be recorded in a video	2025-02-15	2025-06-15	English
Data Harmonization Tools	ICCS	Manual, PPT, Video	2025-02-01	2025-06-17	English
DATAMITE Data Preparation and Sharing in the Data Spaces	E-REDES	Series of short movies, Moodle course	2025-02-01	2025-09-30	English, Portuguese
Getting to know the fairness data tool	UCC	Series of short movies	2025-06-21	2025-10-27	English
Data Product Composition and Anonymisation	CERTH	Documentation, Live or recorded sessions	2025-06-21	2025-10-27	English

Table 1: Initial list of training courses

4. Use Case Demonstrators

This section describes the different pilots that validate the technological stack of DATAMITE. The pilots are organised around three axes:

1- Data exchange within large corporations

Pilot 1 focuses on the accessibility to data of multiple domains and its exchange within a conglomerate of companies – Gimeno Group.

Pilot 2 focuses on the exchange of data within a large company – OTE, where data is stored over different data lakes. The main goal is to facilitate how data is exchanged and consumed within the company.

2- Data exchange through (energy) Data Spaces

In Pilot 3, HEDNO aims to enhance its internal data management while testing the use of data spaces to improve data exchange with data providers. Among others, they validate data governance and quality tools.

Pilot 4 has a two-fold purpose. On the one hand, E-REDES aims to improve the technological stack they are exploiting. On the other hand, they will test the use of data spaces as a potential new environment to offer their open data.

3- Interaction with other initiatives

Pilot 5, led by PSNC, focuses on the governance quality and exploitation of agrifood data from the eDWIN platform. The main goal is to improve the way data is managed while improving, as well as the mechanisms to improve its quality. Complementarily, plugins to publish data into data markets for trading are under validation.

Pilot 6 validates the integration of DATAMITE with the AIOD platform. To do so, CINECA, also aiming to improve how it internally manages the data of its HPC infrastructure, will validate the plugins to share datasets into the European AIOD platform.

More detailed information about the different pilots is provided in the following sections. This information includes aspects such as a description of the pilots, including their architecture and their test scenarios, the current implementation status, references to architecture, training material plans, initial feedback on the DATAMITE platform, including the performance and usability of the DATAMITE framework, and updates on the KPIs and the datasets. Sections are not the same for

each pilot. This is to allow accurate and clear representation of achieved advancement that varies among them.

4.1. Pilot 1 - Corporate Multi-Domain Data Exchange with EDIH support

The Gimeno Group (GIDI) is a corporation composed of many individual companies that cover diverse areas within the citizen services sector. Since its foundation, the growth of the corporation has been constant. The growth trajectory has branched into two main areas: one centred on hospitality, with Intur as its most representative company; the other centred on services, with FACSA and OBREMO as the most notable.

Traditionally, although all companies belong to the same corporation, they operate in isolation as modular units with their own vision and objectives. Currently, incipient strategies for data warehouse unification are in their earliest steps.

DATAMITE can become the cornerstone for connecting architectures and systems and complement the deployment of the group's centralised architecture. In this sense, the selected components of DATAMITE would act as an 'information broker', capable of rapidly displaying the information available in the different departments that make up the companies of the group, ensuring transparency and visibility of the available data and revealing the hidden synergies between the companies.

DATAMITE will offer the possibility to access a Marketplace with detailed information regarding the different published datasets, providing a quick glance at the potential of the utility in a specific use case or at the level of exploration of new products and scenarios by the Data Scientist team of the group.

Likewise, it will offer a quick way to access and download the target data, always maintaining the highest security measures when carrying out the relevant exchanges.

Current situation and future vision

As mentioned in the previous section, the group is made up of more than 40 companies. The sectors in which these companies operate are very diverse and range from comprehensive water management to the field of catering and accommodation. Likewise, we could divide these companies into two well-differentiated groups: on the one hand, we have companies like FACSA or OBREMO, which operate today in the market, offering their services to both private entities

and Public Administrations; on the other hand, we find companies like GIDITEK, which carry out their activity by independently supporting and servicing other companies in the group.

In any case, and most relevant to keep in mind, is that until very recently, the strategy has been to keep companies completely isolated from each other in different aspects and fields. Although a corporate-level strategy has always been followed that links all the companies, each has maintained its vision and strategy focused on its activity, as well as its business objectives, along with its own income statement. Already in a more technological aspect, until relatively recently, there has been a certain degree of independence in terms of choosing the most convenient technologies and architectures for the field of action of these companies, with GIDITEK being the trusted technological partner when it comes to tackling innovation and technology update projects.

Attending to both a commercial and market strategy, the possibility for companies to act independently is essential to be competitive in very different sectors, offering high flexibility and adaptability to the changing conditions of the corresponding sectors in which they operate. However, in recent stages, this strategy has been questioned and has led to a strategic change at the corporate level. Although the independent operational capacity of each company is intended to be maintained, in other areas, such as technology, greater convergence is sought. This strategic change aims to facilitate access to new technologies more dynamically and with centralised control of architectures. In this case, GIDITEK would become the central axis of this new paradigm.

Under this new framework, a set of new projects is located, among which those specifically focused on data management stand out. Today, the design and deployment of a new centralised architecture based on the Big Data paradigm will offer guarantees of management and control of information quality, centralising the persistence of data from the different companies in the same location.

Role of DATAMITE in the current corporate context

One of the most relevant and advantageous aspects of having a large number of companies in the group, as well as being integrated into such differentiated sectors, is the availability of highly diversified and valuable data sources, both internal and external. While this is an advantage when competing in certain areas, the truth is that the isolation in which many of the companies operate affects access to valuable data and information. These barriers are both technological and operational and, in some cases, legal.

The past few years have demonstrated the advantage of having these databases when it comes to competing and generating synergies in certain sectors. While operational and legal barriers may require other types of actions and corporate-level changes, technological and access security barriers can be eliminated using software tools and applications. It is in this precise and particular aspect that DATAMITE can offer and provide all its potential, becoming the cornerstone of a new paradigm in the field of information access for users located in different companies of the group. The success of this pilot implementation of DATAMITE will lead to it becoming part of the new corporate architecture, integrating not only its modules but also the best practices it offers in managing data access and sharing.

Furthermore, the current context focuses solely on indirect data exploitation, improving competitiveness through the exploitation of synergies between companies in the group. However, in a medium-to-long-term scenario, the interest in direct data exploitation for economic benefits from its direct sale is clear. This is why DATAMITE has become an essential tool for "evangelising" everything related to data monetisation. In this way, it becomes the guide for the development of a future data monetisation strategy within the group.

Pilot 1 briefing

In Pilot 1, in which companies from the Gimeno Group directly participate, a DATAMITE experience of data exchange between companies through DATAMITE's intermediation is expected to be carried out.

The companies participating in this experience are three:

- **FACSA:** a company specialising in the comprehensive management of the water cycle. With more than 150 years of experience, it currently offers services in the management of supplies in different socioeconomic and demographic areas.
- **OBREMO:** a company that offers services in various fields of telecommunications and the energy sector. Today, these services range from operations for large telecommunications companies to the management and maintenance of facilities involved in the production of both renewable and conventional energy.
- **GIDITEK:** A technology company within the Gimeno Group fundamentally responsible for offering communication technology services to other companies. It is also configured as the engine of innovation and technological change for the rest of the companies. Among the areas covered by its projects are artificial intelligence, design and deployment of Big Data architecture, and data governance.

During the pilot, a dataset-sharing channel between data-producing companies will be developed. In this sense, both FACSA and OBREMO, in the role of data producers, will make impactful datasets available to other companies in the group within the scope of the pilot experience. DATAMITE's modules will always be managed by GIDITEK. Likewise, a simulation of the exploitation and enrichment of the data offered by these companies will be carried out by a technology company. In this sense, GIDITEK will be the company that develops this role.

Also, the ITI will be configured as an external organisation that offers the possibility of deploying the modules in a non-local environment. Additionally, it will have the role of an intermediary for data exchange with other observatories or public organisations. This fact is especially relevant since, in many public contracts, the requirement for the public sharing of certain data has been increasingly demanded in recent months and must be fulfilled obligatorily and unfailingly by the companies awarded the contracts.

4.1.1. Test Scenarios

In this section, the different scenarios used in the testing of the DATAMITE modules are presented.

In general, this section pretends to emulate the behaviour of each of the different actors that will be part of the data exchange experience between the group companies.

Likewise, the aim is to emulate a process of data enrichment and integration from machine learning modelling to improve or complete information related to a specific aspect or sector. This last practice will be commonly carried out by technology companies such as GIDITEK, which hold a monopoly on the use of advanced modelling and artificial intelligence within the core of the Gimeno Group.

4.1.1.1. Scenario 1: Ingestion and publication of a Dataset for subsequent access and use by third parties

The data provider from FACSA has approval from the Chief Security Officer to publish a set of datasets that they are certain will be useful for other companies in the group, with the possibility that these datasets may later be published in a public environment for monetisation (optional).

This data has been processed to ensure minimal coherence and cohesion considerations. However, there may be certain errors or issues that need to be addressed before publication, and at this point, they have not been resolved by the team of data scientists responsible.

Additionally, the data has been anonymised by removing any reference to a natural person or sensitive entity. Nevertheless, the CSO has decided that the data must also be anonymised in the field of geolocation, as it may be sensitive in relation to working with certain clients, as well as in case this data ends up being monetised in a hypothetical future. The diagram showing Scenario 1 as a process diagram can be consulted in the Figure 3.

Figure 3: Testing scenario 1 diagram

4.1.1.2. Scenario 2: Exploring and accessing published datasets

In OBREMO, the team responsible for data processing and production has received a request to obtain data related to a specific aspect of the integrated water cycle. If this information is available within the group, it will reduce costs when generating this data within the contract under study, and it will allow the studies and bids team to present a more attractive and competitive offer.

The person in charge of the search will access the catalogue of published datasets, search the database as usual, and access the metadata of the published data. Among all the datasets published by FACSA, some will not be visible to OBREMO. Among those that are visible, they will access the one required for their use case and download the summary statistics to share with the studies and bids team.

With their approval, they will request access for the download from OBREMO, which will grant approval and proceed with the data download. Figure 4 shows the process related to the development of this one test.

Figure 4: Testing scenario 2 diagram

4.1.1.3. Scenario 3: Data enrichment of published datasets by third parties on published data

In this case, GIDITEK is developing an advanced method for the regularisation and normalisation of time series. This process is not covered by DATAMITE, so they proceed to test it on one of the datasets containing time series to which they have access.

To do this, they access the catalogue and the types of fields that make up each dataset to verify that it correctly presents a time series. They also confirm that the periodicity, in this case, is irregular.

They propose to apply their model to this dataset, specifically to its numerical fields. With the corresponding permission from the person responsible for the data, they access the data, connect it to their model, and produce a new regularised dataset. This data is made available to the other companies in the group, uploading it to the platform in a manner like that described in Scenario 1.

Additionally, taking advantage of this visit, they discovered the presence of a dataset with photovoltaic production data from a power plant, which is currently managed by OBREMO. IoTsens, the IoT company of our corporation group, has weather stations in the area and owns this information. Since GIDI has a predictive model that allows them to estimate photovoltaic production based on weather conditions following the scheme of a virtual sensor, they decided to leverage this information to generate a new dataset of predictions that will also increase in size periodically. They also decide to make it available to OBREMO from the DATAMITE platform itself. Figure 5 and Figure 6 refer to the scenario described in the present section.

Figure 5: Testing scenario 3a diagram

Figure 6: Testing scenario 3b diagram

4.1.2. Solution implementation

In this section, the procedure followed for the deployment of the test environment of the scenarios mentioned in the previous section is discussed. As already mentioned, the objective was to develop a complete emulation of what the workflow will be like when generating three fundamental actions by the agents in charge of the system:

1. Data contribution: mainly carried out by those companies that produce data or own it. In this pilot case, the companies are FACSA and OBREMO, but generally, any company with access to architecture and the possibility of publishing relevant data is considered a data producer.
2. Data extraction: This task is primarily aimed at companies or departments interested in extracting and accessing relevant data that meets the specific needs at the pertinent time. Therefore, while this role will be developed by those technology or consultancy companies that require enriching the available data stack for a specific project or task, any company in the group can carry out this task universally.
3. Data enrichment: This task is especially limited to those companies, such as GIDITEK, that have the appropriate knowledge to proceed with the enrichment of data published in different facets using both traditional and advanced analytical methodologies.

The environment deployed for the development of this pilot has been based on establishing the two main roles that will have access to the system. A system composed of three virtual machines hosted in the group's data centre has been deployed. Each of them will assume a specific role within the testing process. These machines have been adequately configured for the role they will carry out both in terms of hardware and software.

The specifications of the machines are as follows:

- Four processing cores
- 32 GB of physical memory
- 50 GB of storage
- OS Ubuntu Linux 24.04 LTS

The 3 machines are:

- Virtual Machine A (Dataset Publisher): This virtual machine will be responsible for managing the publication of data that will be offered through the data sharing modules.
- Virtual Machine B (Request Receiver): This virtual machine will manage the data requests made on the DATAMITE Marketplace module.
- Virtual Machine C (DATAMITE Infrastructure): This machine is responsible for hosting the various modules that make up the DATAMITE system.

The technologies used for deploying testing actions are based on modular architectures that aim to offer connection points between the various agents involved in the experience. In this case, the agents are represented by the virtual machines that have been deployed.

Apart from deployed systems related with Gimeno architecture, which have been detailed above these lines, DATAMITE is the main framework for testing operations. Following, we enumerate the DATAMITE modules which are tested in this pilot:

- DATAMITE Data Sharing module.
- DATAMITE Data Security module.
- DATAMITE Data Quality module.

Below is a detailed overview of the different technologies along with the role they play in architecture:

- Kubernetes + Docker: These are two tools that work symbiotically at a lower level. They are used to deploy the different virtual components that are part of the testing architecture.
- PostgreSQL: a relational database engine that is necessary for emulating the most widely used storage technology within the group companies. While there are other relational persistence engines, this is the primary representative and, thus, has been selected for the tests.
- MongoDB: non-relational, document-based database engine. This technology was chosen due to its high demand among group companies for data storage requiring horizontal scaling.
- Cassandra: Companies like IoTsens, a group company specialising in device and data management with "internet of things" technology, handle large amounts of time-series data. These time-series are currently stored using this database engine, making its integration into DATAMITE experiences essential.
- Elastic: This technology has been added as an advanced search engine for optional deployment and testing if requested by the group companies.
- Django RestFramework: Services destined for data connection and integration in the testing context have been developed using REST technology. An API with various specific "end points" has been created, converting them into access points for different datasets. This way, the availability of services allowing external data queries, which DATAMITE or other external agents can connect to, will also be emulated for group companies.

4.1.3. Training Materials planned

There are two types of users who will interact with the platform: on one hand, we have the management users, those with full handling and access capacity for the data stored and who are

fundamentally in charge of the administrative tasks of the platform itself; and on the other hand, we have the users with restricted access. This user will be the most common user and will essentially be searching for new data or even contributing new data to the system. Since they are the most common user, the training processes will be exclusively directed at these personnel. Training will be carried out by the GIDITEK team.

For this, previous experiences carried out in other projects will be taken into account for the development of training materials and methodology. It usually consists of a demonstration session in which interested users receive an invitation to participate. In this sense, the team that participated in the DATAMITE project will be responsible for developing and carrying out the content of this session. The session will consist, firstly, of an initial presentation indicating the key pillars and principles on which the project is based. During this more theoretical presentation, multimedia resources such as audio-visual presentations and PowerPoint will be used.

In the second part of this session, a practical demonstration of the use of the application in the different relevant aspects of the functionalities of interest for pilot 1 will be given. The use cases presented during this demonstration will derive from the use cases presented in this document, as they have been designed in response to the predominant type of use by the different group companies and departments interested in the system.

The session will conclude with an internal debate during which doubts and suggestions will be raised by the participants, addressing both the operation and usage of the tool, as well as expressing future needs that may be included in future developments or as an evolution of the tool.

Additionally, it is not ruled out the use of materials generated by other organizations or pilots within the project as additional documentation and materials that will be made available, with the appropriate permissions from the creators of such documentation to the departments and users with access to DATAMITE.

4.1.4. Test Campaign

The development of the test campaigns is being carried out in two different periods, both located throughout the year 2025. Through these tests, it has been intended to evaluate different aspects related to the internal functioning and behaviour of the DATAMITE project within the group today.

The pillars that are intended to be evaluated are the following:

- Integrity of the solution

-
- Compatibility with the group's solutions
 - Penetration in operations

Next, emphasis is placed today on the different aspects that will be assessed during these test periods of the tool:

- **Technical aspects:** Technically, it aims to evaluate those parameters that allow a judgment on the suitability of the solution as a software tool. The robustness of the system, ease of deployment and management, technological performance, etc., will be considered. Regarding its compatibility with the new architecture of the group, the possibility of its integration, or at least some of the modules that compose it, will be analysed as part of the solution.
- **Operational aspects:** An internal analysis is carried out to determine future viability in terms of the operations carried out in the different departments likely to be incorporated. In this sense, a study will be carried out with requests and/or suggestions from these departments when seeking improvements in the system's capabilities. Although these improvements are likely outside the scope of the DATAMITE project, they may be of interest in clarifying the project's evolution and growth, ensuring its future life within organizations like ours. This exercise will be of utmost necessity to clarify the future of data monetisation in the context of the Gimeno Group.
- **Social and economic aspects:** This context includes all analyses carried out to clarify the level of acceptance and knowledge by users in the different departments likely to be incorporated into the project. It is closely related to the previous section on training materials and will be carried out exclusively through internal work. It will become the thermometer indicating the level of acceptance and knowledge in a corporate context today to determine the future measures of greatest interest. In this section, all internal analyses carried out in work packages such as work package number 4 are of particular interest.

The development of the tests is carried out through the scenarios described in previous sections, emulating their operation through exercises developed by people from the involved departments and subsequently offering the results for review in a second round and later, in a successive round during the summer months.

4.1.5. Feedback for improving design

The technical results related to the performance of DATAMITE within the context of the evaluation of the test scenarios are reflected in a report, detailing each point and element evaluated by the agents.

Additionally, this includes aspects related to other sections mentioned previously that are unrelated to the technical evaluation of the solution and will merely provide information about the penetration of the concepts of information exchange and data monetisation that underpin the DATAMITE project.

Alongside these results, a set of suggestions and requests from companies will be included to guide the second-round evaluation of the tool's performance.

4.1.6. Performance and usability of the DATAMITE framework

The following Table 2/Figure 2 presents the evaluation KPIs within the organisation for the first iteration of 2025:

KPI	Description	Baseline	Target
KPI1	Number of Active Users	0	3
KPI2	Number of Dataset Downloads	0	~10
KPI3	Frequency of Access	0	~20/month
KPI4	Number of Datasets Available	0	>10
KPI5	Data Quality Score based on quality factors (completeness, accuracy, and relevance)	0	Qualitative assessment
KPI6	Retention Rate (number of users who return to the platform after a first access)	0	3

Table 2: Pilot 1 KPIs.

The KPIs for the second evaluation phase are the same, along with those suggested by the expertise of the partners.

The objectives for the second round will be established at the end of the first evaluation round, together with the results obtained and the suggestions provided by the testers.

4.2. Pilot 2 - Corporate Multi-Site Data Exchange

The OTE Group manages an extensive volume of data and holds a leading position in the telecommunications sector within Greece. Historically, the organisation has been at the forefront of landline communication operations and has played a critical role in the country's transition to digital infrastructure. During the early stages of digitisation, landlines were not only central to

communication but also served as identifiers for unique services and physical locations, thereby establishing a link between digital services and geographical or residential identities.

Over the past two decades, the OTE Group has significantly expanded its telecommunications operations, introducing a variety of technical services and assets that extend beyond communication. These offerings now encompass a comprehensive range of digital interactions, facilitating seamless engagement between customers, businesses, and the public sector. However, this rapid expansion necessitated the integration and interoperability of a diverse type of services to deliver personalised and value-added experiences to customers.

Strategic Data Vision & Compliance

The integration of AI into all levels of organisational processes fundamentally reshapes operational models. Telecom operators, including OTE Group, are uniquely positioned to expand their service offerings by leveraging the vast amounts of data they host. This data can be utilised not only to develop new services but also to refine and optimize existing processes and products.

At the core of this transformation lies the recognition that AI's effectiveness is inherently tied to data availability. The extensive repositories maintained by organizations represent an asset for generating innovative insights and breakthrough services. However, harnessing this potential requires a well-defined strategic framework and a clear vision.

Beyond a vertical implementation approach, AI adoption must also be structured through a horizontal process, ensuring cross-departmental integration. To achieve this, a dedicated governing body or an appointed leader should oversee the orchestration of AI-driven initiatives, ensuring alignment with organizational objectives and building a coherent and robust data-driven ecosystem.

Towards that direction, **the creation of the Chief Data (Strategy) Officer (CDO) role** within OTE Group (Figure 7), introduces a transformative approach to the company's data management and strategic utilization. This pivotal position is tasked with the development and execution of a comprehensive data strategy that aligns with the organization's broader business objectives. Central to this role is the deployment of strategic initiatives aimed at leveraging data to foster innovation, secure a competitive edge, and drive business growth.

At the core of the CDO's responsibilities is the establishment of robust data governance frameworks, policies, and processes. These measures are crucial for ensuring the effective, secure, and compliant management of data across the organization. By instituting these

frameworks, the CDO safeguards the integrity and privacy of data, thereby mitigating risks and aligning with prevailing regulatory requirements.

Moreover, the CDO oversees the enhancement of the organization's data analytics capabilities. This oversight includes the development and deployment of advanced analytics tools and methodologies to extract valuable insights from vast data repositories. Through those analytical endeavours, the CDO enables informed decision-making processes and enhances the company's business intelligence capabilities, thereby facilitating a data-driven culture within OTE.

To streamline data governance and management within such a complex enterprise, the CDO is set to introduce specialized versions of data marts tailored to the organization's unique needs. This approach ensures that each department's data requirements are extensively evaluated and fulfilled in alignment with the overarching data strategy.

Data Owner (Business User) is the responsible for dataset that are provided, authorizing what datasets will be shared to whom and for how long.

Data Consumer (Business User) is the user who will have access to use the data for business related tasks and decision-making processes.

Data Provider is responsible to prepare, make available, integrate and provide needed datasets / information to data consumers based on directions of data owners.

System Administrator is responsible for the operation, management and maintenance of the installed DATAMITE instance.

Security/Privacy Responsible is responsible for setting the privacy and security policies, guiding and consulting users concerning related topics and overseeing their implementation.

Data Governance Responsible develops, consults, monitors and enforces data governance policies and practices (including Data Quality).

Chief Data (Strategy) Officer (CDO) develops and oversees company's data strategy, ensuring that data assets are leveraged for maximum value and align with overall business objectives.

Figure 7: Chief Data Officer role to AI-driven application formation

Despite its ambitious trajectory, the rapid growth of OTE Group's service portfolio has been accompanied by certain challenges. Many of the newly introduced services were deployed without thorough testing or establishment of well-structured data models. In a large-scale data environment, such challenges can lead to logical inconsistencies that may trigger cascading failures, requiring substantial time and resources to mitigate. Furthermore, those discrepancies

can occasionally propagate to end users, negatively affecting the customer experience - a critical factor in the highly competitive telecommunications sector.

As illustrated in Figure 8, the case study of the OTE Group involves a scenario in which a data analyst seeks to identify inconsistencies across three distinct data repositories within the organisation. These repositories correspond to different operational units, each one managing critical aspects of the organisation’s infrastructure and services.

Figure 8: Pilot 2 databases' schema

The first repository, managed by the **Registry Unit**, contains the organisation's customer data. This repository includes personal identification details of customers, their loyalty status, and

information related to their relationship with the organisation. Specifically, it tracks the number of services utilized by the customer, the duration of the relationship, and the total expenditure incurred by the customer on OTE Group services.

The second repository, overseen by the **Infrastructure Unit**, facilitates the management of the organisation's hardware and physical infrastructure essential for service delivery to end users. This repository maintains detailed information on the physical and operational aspects of the network, such as Fiber-to-the-Home (FTTH) cabinets, copper cables, DSLAMs, and network operation centres. It encompasses data on the customer's router, including the model and firmware version, as well as the physical communication medium (e.g., fibre, copper, satellite) and its connection path to the network centre. Additionally, this repository records physical constraints and operational analytics of the network lines, such as maximum bandwidth capacity, error rates, power supply limitations, and the presence or absence of Uninterruptible Power Supplies (UPS) at endpoints or intermediate nodes.

The third repository, maintained by the **Accounting Unit**, contains billing and financial information related to customer accounts. This repository includes details about invoicing, total sales per customer, and specific information that must be shared with the customer, such as contract terms and the Service Level Agreements (SLAs) associated with their subscription.

Since much of the information originates from different organisational units with distinct business goals and priorities, numerous failures arise due to the lack of interoperability in such a dynamic environment, where changes occur on a weekly basis. The competitive nature of the telecommunications market drives rapid processes and transformations, which inevitably lead to inconsistencies in data entry and discrepancies between various data stores. Unlike data entry errors, inconsistencies between data stores often involve logical errors that are significantly more challenging to detect and resolve.

The initial approach to address those challenges involves creating a unified metadata model and a centralised metadata repository. This solution allows data to be managed through a common interface, platform, and language. The choice of a unified language is particularly critical, as the technical limitations and priorities of each unit often dictate the selection of data repositories. For instance, performance may be the absolute priority in one case, while security and privacy in another one. Similarly, a relational data format optimised for structured data might suit one scenario, while a semi-structured format that offers flexibility is preferred in another one. Some

data repositories prioritize read-intensive operations, while others must support frequent updates. The diversity of use cases makes it unrealistic to rely on a one-size-fits-all solution.

Further complicating the situation is the constant influx of new services and shifting objectives of organizational units, driven by the evolving market. These changes necessitate frequent adaptations to remain competitive and State-of-the-Art. Current solutions, which are often based on traditional models and architectures from the past two decades, face significant shortcomings. They are not AI-enabled and fail to incorporate features essential for modern data management. Moreover, the DevSecOps paradigm has transformed the way enterprises manage data, necessitating structural rather than superficial changes.

Middleware that automates or semi-automates data integration is crucial in addressing these challenges. Additionally, a unified query language is essential to ensure sustainability and usability across the organization. Simplifying the learning curve and minimizing training requirements are critical in a fast-paced market where rapid adaptation is necessary.

To remain competitive, organizations must focus on developing a unified platform capable of supporting diverse data warehouse architectures while implementing a standardized, user-friendly programming language to streamline database interactions. Ensuring security and enabling efficient development of data marts that can be readily distributed to analysts for detailed examination is also vital. Moreover, it is essential to support high-performance processing of both OLAP and OLTP workloads, incorporate AI capabilities to expose metadata and features for modern applications, and present these capabilities through an intuitive and comprehensive user interface where critical information is easily accessible.

4.2.1. Test Scenarios

As the complexity of data schemas increases, the implementation of safeguard controls becomes essential. Inconsistencies within different repositories not only complicate system operations but also disrupt the enterprise workflow. This issue is particularly critical for the customer excellence department, which relies on accurate and reliable data to deliver personalised services at competitive prices that appeal to end users.

Unfortunately, such inconsistencies can significantly affect the customer experience - an aspect in which enterprises invest substantial resources throughout the customer journey. Any disruptions or errors arising from data inconsistencies may destroy customer trust and satisfaction, ultimately jeopardising the organisation's efforts to maintain long-term, cooperative relationships with its clients.

4.2.1.1. Scenario 1: OLAP Dimension

The first scenario involves the development of dedicated data marts that integrate information from various repositories to enable analysts to identify inconsistencies and modify tables to ensure accuracy and alignment across all departments. In this scenario, the Data Governance department assumes the responsibility of creating a data mart while considering critical factors, such as the repositories where inconsistencies may exist, complaints from customers or personnel regarding inaccurate data, and the quality metadata derived from these tables. All these processes are conducted with strict adherence to security and privacy protocols.

The core concept is to provide periodic snapshots of data, allowing analysts to identify inconsistencies and derive rules that enforce conformity across repositories. This data mart is distributed to analysts, who then investigate discrepancies within specific views of the repositories. The insights generated from this analysis are subsequently sent to the Data Compliance department for validation. Here, these insights are examined to ensure they are accurate, do not duplicate existing rules, and are not already addressed by other mechanisms. Once reviewed and refined in consultation with relevant departments, the new rules are implemented in production, leading to updates in the data repositories to resolve the identified inconsistencies.

This scenario represents a direct application of DevOps principles to data management, creating a secure and systematic architecture for Continuous Integration and Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) in the data domain. The data mesh approach is adopted to transition towards a data space environment, which ensures systematic compliance with emerging EU regulations and strategies for data exposure. This structured methodology enhances data accuracy, interoperability, and scalability in complex data environments.

4.2.1.2. Scenario 2: Visual and Strategic Dimension

The second scenario focuses on addressing the challenges of identifying relationships between data repositories, tables, and schemas by leveraging metadata exploration. In this approach, senior data analysts and architects delve into metadata to abstractly identify potential sources of inconsistencies and their root causes. The primary goal is to develop a strategic roadmap for prioritising data warehouses and organisational departments that require immediate attention.

This prioritisation may be driven by strategic factors, such as maximising the enterprise's revenue by concentrating the efforts accordingly, improving customer relationships by enhancing customer

success stories and satisfaction, or reducing complaints and mitigating potential fines arising from inaccurate database information. This strategy ensures that resources are allocated efficiently to address the most critical areas with the greatest impact on organisational goals.

A key element of this scenario is the use of visual analytics to explore various cases and identify unique characteristics. Visual representations of metadata and insights provide a comprehensive overview that aids in understanding complex relationships and patterns across repositories. This visual approach is particularly significant when presenting findings and strategies to the higher levels of the enterprise. Clear and engaging visualisations ensure that metadata insights, data inconsistencies, and strategic guidelines are communicated effectively, aligning technical analyses with the enterprise's broader goals and facilitating informed decision-making.

By coupling metadata exploration with visual analytics and aligning findings with strategic objectives, this scenario puts emphasis on optimising data warehouse management and ensuring that the enterprise remains agile and competitive in a data-driven environment.

4.2.1.3. Scenario 3: OLTP Dimension

The third scenario deals with the day-to-day operations of the enterprise, where the need for accurate, real-time solutions is critical. In this context, it is vital to ensure that instant changes can be made without being impeded by security or technical restrictions. This process involves personnel with the appropriate accreditation to control and modify data, combining information from multiple sources to resolve specific issues, typographical errors, or inconsistencies as they are identified.

A key challenge for OTE Group is that its customer data is distributed across multiple IT systems, making it difficult to establish a unified customer view that supports the organisation's CRM strategy. This unified view is essential for optimising sales, service, and marketing processes. Consequently, the implementation of a continuous customer data improvement and quality assurance process within a centralised customer view is crucial for ensuring consistent and reliable data across the enterprise.

In this scenario, as with the OLAP dimension, the ideal solution involves using a middleware platform capable of adhering to regulatory restrictions while providing a standardised environment. With this platform, employees can perform standardised queries, preferably using SQL, to manage daily processes and correct misinformation or errors effectively. Such an environment would allow for real-time adjustments without compromising compliance or security.

This capability is particularly relevant in scenarios where the enterprise aims to attract new customers or upsell additional services to existing customers by leveraging established relationships. Human oversight remains invaluable in this process, as experienced personnel are best equipped to identify and resolve logical issues that automated systems might ignore. For example, during the preparation of an offer or while reviewing a customer profile, any errors or inconsistencies that arise can be immediately addressed. This proactive approach ensures that potential customer dissatisfaction is mitigated and the user experience remains positive, safeguarding the enterprise's relationship with its clients.

The integration of real-time correction capabilities with robust middleware and a unified customer view enhances operational efficiency and strengthens the organisation's ability to respond dynamically to both internal needs and customer demands.

4.2.2. Solution implementation

The evolving landscape of modern applications and data management necessitates a paradigm shift toward a data-centric approach, wherein data is the primary asset, and all supporting infrastructures serve to facilitate its efficient utilisation. The DATAMITE framework aligns with this vision by establishing a structured and secure data exchange ecosystem that prioritises data governance, quality assurance, and regulatory compliance.

The core objective of DATAMITE is to streamline multi-site data exchange processes through the implementation of a metadata-driven repository, which significantly reduces the complexity of data governance. This enables organisations to enforce fine-grained, role-based access controls while maintaining a centralised architecture for defining and managing data quality standards.

During the pilot execution phase, the Data Governance module of DATAMITE serves as a unifying layer, ensuring a consistent interpretation of business terminology across diverse data sources for both technical and business users. Simultaneously, the Data Quality module enforces predefined freshness and accuracy standards, thereby boosting confidence in the usability and reliability of datasets. Furthermore, the Security and Data Sharing modules facilitate secure and policy-compliant data exchange, ensuring adherence to General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) requirements and internal security policies via a centralised framework.

To assess the real-world impact and effectiveness of the DATAMITE framework, its deployment should be validated against an enterprise-grade use case that integrates multiple heterogeneous data platforms and delivers tangible business value. A representative case study involves the Predict Next Billing Interaction scenario, which aims to identify customers likely to contact call

centres regarding billing issues (e.g., bill shock) after receiving an invoice. By proactively detecting those scenarios, the organisation can initiate pre-emptive engagement strategies, ultimately improving customer satisfaction and retention.

One of the primary challenges in this use case is the integration of diverse data sources to generate the required feature sets for predictive analytics. To ensure feasibility while managing system complexity, the pilot implementation adopts a Minimum Viable Product (MVP) approach, enabling an efficient Proof-of-Concept (PoC) validation without necessitating a full-scale rollout. This methodology allows the DATAMITE framework to be tested under realistic conditions while optimising resource utilisation.

The insights derived from the pilot will serve as a foundation for scaling the solution across a broader dataset, incorporating all relevant data sources, and refining predictive accuracy. Additionally, the DATAMITE framework is designed to be extensible, allowing its architecture to support other PoCs with similar data integration needs. Its modular design facilitates ad hoc analytics, data visualisation, and self-service reporting, thereby empowering organisations with a scalable and democratised data ecosystem. Moreover, the methodology can be replicated across industries with analogous data governance challenges, such as telecommunications, finance, and healthcare, thus accelerating deployment timelines and enhancing cross-sector data interoperability.

By fostering a holistic and secure data exchange environment, the DATAMITE framework enables organisations to unlock new data-driven insights, improve decision-making, and ensure regulatory compliance in an increasingly complex data landscape. The integration of OTE Group's data architecture with the DATAMITE framework is achieved by aligning the existing data mart structure of OTE's traditional model with the data product paradigm introduced by DATAMITE. This transition is not only compatible but also in accordance with the European Union's vision for data spaces, enhancing interoperability, security, and efficiency.

OTE's existing model for data-driven applications and services is structured around a two-layer approach (Figure 9). The first layer is responsible for optimising data storage by organising data into a well-structured data mart derived from OTE's data lake. This data mart is designed to serve specific business objectives, particularly supporting analysts and decision-makers. To ensure consistency and accessibility, the data mart is governed by a policy engine and library that transforms it into a structured and consumable product. Once structured, it becomes available

through an internal data mart marketplace, where employees with the necessary permissions can explore and request access according to their needs.

The second layer governs access to these data marts through Role-Based Access Control (RBAC), ensuring that query results are tailored based on the user's role. When an employee retrieves a data mart, they can apply designated AI algorithms or conduct analytical queries on the dataset. At this stage, additional security layers verify that the user has the required credentials and authentication privileges before granting access to sensitive data. This approach enhances privacy and security and aligns with organisational policies.

Figure 9: OTE's existing two-layer approach model

While this model is effective in ensuring data security and compliance, it presents significant limitations in terms of flexibility and rapid prototyping. The bureaucratic procedures required to approve access, modify datasets, and align data needs with business objectives often result in prolonged decision-making cycles. This recursive process involves multiple meetings across various layers of design and governance, creating delays that may cause too much damage in the fast-paced AI era. In many cases, the extensive time required to identify, justify, and approve a data need can lead to missed opportunities, as the dynamic nature of AI-driven applications demands immediate adaptability to market shifts.

To address these challenges, the DATAMITE framework introduces a more agile and efficient approach by replacing rigid, hierarchical governance with a modular and data-product-driven architecture. By decoupling data governance from traditional bureaucratic constraints and enabling a more responsive and dynamic data-sharing ecosystem, DATAMITE empowers organisations to embrace rapid prototyping and experimentation without compromising security and compliance. This shift ensures that organisations such as OTE Group can remain competitive in an environment where data-driven insights and AI applications must be deployed swiftly to capture emerging opportunities and maintain technological leadership.

Towards implementation of the vision through DATAMITE Reference Architecture

The transition from traditional data management models to an advanced, AI-driven ecosystem requires a structured reformation of existing architectures. The DATAMITE Reference Architecture (Figure 10) provides a comprehensive framework for achieving this transformation by addressing key challenges in data governance, security, and scalability. By redefining data structuring, metadata utilisation, and the transition to a data product and data space paradigm, DATAMITE framework enables organisations to enhance operational efficiency, streamline data accessibility, and foster real-time adaptability in an increasingly dynamic digital landscape.

The core module that implements these concepts into the DATAMITE Reference Architecture (Figure 10) is the **Data Product Composition**. This module is designed to accept one or more datasets as input, enabling users to merge them into a unified file by comparing rows and columns or selectively retaining or removing specific attributes.

More specifically, the module automatically analyses the input files, providing detailed metadata such as file names, column names, data types, the number of entries per field, and overall dataset size. Additionally, it facilitates dataset comparison by examining structural similarities across columns and rows, enabling merging operations based on predefined criteria. Users have the flexibility to determine which columns should be retained or removed before finalizing the integration. Upon completion, the module generates and provides access to the merged dataset, ensuring a streamlined and efficient data processing workflow.

Figure 10: DATAMITE reference architecture

The DATAMITE reformation of the traditional two-layer approach can be structured as a sequence of transformative steps. The first fundamental step is the establishment of a unified data format that ensures consistency in data governance, allowing for seamless restructuring and adaptation without dependencies on external services. These services often introduce bottlenecks in data and security workflows, as they must continuously align with overarching processes while maintaining up-to-date policies and access controls. Furthermore, governance responsibilities are frequently fragmented among different entities, leading to inconsistencies in policy enforcement and security management.

The second critical step involves the implicit integration of metadata governance. Traditionally, metadata is managed at the database level rather than being centrally controlled through governance tools. This limitation results in fragmented data insights and restricts advanced data mining functionalities. A unified approach to metadata governance would enhance the accuracy and comprehensiveness of data analysis, facilitating better decision-making and more refined business intelligence models. By embedding metadata management into the governance framework, organisations can achieve higher transparency, improved data traceability, and increased automation in regulatory compliance.

The final and most significant step is the transition from a data-mart-oriented model to a data product and data space paradigm. In the traditional approach, the data mart is optimised for specific tasks, serving as a well-structured repository for analytics and reporting. However, in

alignment with the DATAMITE project’s vision, data products are no longer limited to static repositories but instead evolve into dynamic, self-contained assets that incorporate governance mechanisms, live monitoring capabilities, and analytical tools. This shift enables real-time adaptability, ensuring that data products continuously align with business needs and regulatory requirements.

For instance, in a practical business scenario, when the call centre department identifies a need for datasets related to customer satisfaction, loyalty, and revenue metrics, the CDO, in collaboration with the Data Protection Officer (DPO), leverages a Graphical User Interface (GUI) to identify potential data sources across various repositories, such as customer, billing, and product databases. This approach allows for seamless data discovery, validation, and integration, ensuring that business users can access high-quality, policy-compliant datasets without delays caused by traditional bureaucratic procedures.

By adopting the DATAMITE reference architecture, organizations such as OTE Group can move towards a more agile, scalable, and policy-driven data ecosystem, where data is not only a passive asset but an actively governed, continuously evolving resource (Figure 11). This paradigm shift fosters efficient data democratization, enhances cross-functional collaboration, and ensures that AI-driven applications can be deployed in a timely and effective manner.

Figure 11: Model transformation adapting to DATAMITE reference architecture

Utilising tools like Trino for distributed data management, the CDO manipulates the GUI to select appropriate data columns that meet the specific informational requirements, guided by company policies that demand selections based on quality and other criteria. For example, this process involves accessing data considering sparsity thresholds (e.g. sparsity less than 10%), the inclusion of essential contact information (e.g. at least one contact detail, based on the ontology that the metamodel has), considering the region or ageing level (e.g. to be located in Greece where is allowed to offer services over 18 years old), enforcing compliance with GDPR for promotional purposes (has written consent for contacting for those purposes).

Upon finalising the data selection, a corresponding data product is created to precisely address certain needs. This product is being strictly validated by the DPO as well as the security department, and then -if approved- is being made available for consumption in OTE's internal data product marketplace.

There, it is accessible through the data catalogue, allowing for tailored data visibility among different user groups within the organisation. For instance, call centre personnel may be restricted to viewing only recent transactional data, whereas higher-level officials might access comprehensive customer histories. That is enforced at run time level through the access control mechanisms.

This newly introduced approach highlights the CDO's critical role in orchestrating a sophisticated data governance structure that not only supports strategic business objectives but also ensures data privacy and compliance, thereby enhancing OTE's position as a data-forward organisation in the telecommunications industry.

4.2.3. Training Materials planned

Pilot 2 plans to provide training materials related to the Data Product Composition module. More specifically, in the context of Task 2.3, short videos will be prepared to showcase step-by-step the creation of complex data products by simultaneously accessing heterogeneous databases using common SQL queries.

4.2.4. Test Campaign

A comprehensive series of tests are conducted to evaluate the DATAMITE framework effectively. The benchmarking data that are used in this evaluation, include a collection of datasets extracted from the OTE warehouse. These datasets are particularly designed to align closely with the overall schema, structure, and characteristics inherent to the framework's design. A synthetic AI

tool has been developed specifically for this purpose, considering various AI factors and usage scenarios that data analysts may encounter while querying the datasets. The importance of using benchmark datasets and synthetic tools in evaluating frameworks like DATAMITE cannot be underestimated. In fact, benchmark datasets serve as critical references that facilitate the assessment of performance and functionality across different systems, particularly in OLAP and OLTP environments. For instance, studies have shown that well-structured benchmark datasets can significantly enhance the reliability of performance evaluations. Furthermore, synthetic tools can simulate diverse data scenarios, enabling a more robust analysis of how platforms respond to varying workloads and queries.

OLAP dimension scenario

Business Context

A telecom company, such as OTE Group, manages a vast infrastructure composed of network equipment from multiple providers (e.g., Huawei, Cisco, Nokia). This infrastructure supports various telecom services, including VDSL, FTTH, and mobile networks. The company needs to analyse and optimise its network by understanding how different providers perform, identifying missing data issues, and ensuring smooth operations for customers.

Objective of the Evaluation

The primary goal of this evaluation is to analyse the telecom infrastructure and identify key insights regarding network providers, missing data issues, and location-specific deployment trends (Figure 12). More specifically, it aims to determine the number of network infrastructure components deployed by each provider, detect instances where critical billing and order information is missing, and analyse devices deployed in specific regions, particularly those where the “maincabin” identifier starts with "43" (which is the code for Attica region).

By executing that query, OTE Group can detect data inconsistencies, optimise network operations, and improve service provisioning while ensuring that missing financial and order-related data does not lead to revenue loss or compliance violations.

Create Trino Query

Name: Identifying Data Gaps and Trends in Network Infrastructure for

Is Recursive: true

Start Date: 01/01/2025

End Date: 03/11/2025

Interval Hours: 720

Query

```

COUNT(*) AS total_entries,
SUM(CASE WHEN totalbill IS NULL OR totalbill = " THEN 1 ELSE 0 END) AS missing_totalbill_count,
SUM(CASE WHEN orderflag IS NULL OR orderflag = " THEN 1 ELSE 0 END) AS missing_orderflag_count
FROM unified_data
WHERE maincabin LIKE '43%'
GROUP BY networkprovider
ORDER BY total_entries DESC;

```

Notes

The company needs to analyze and optimize its network by understanding how different network providers perform, identifying missing data issues, and ensuring smooth operations for customers.

Execute Save

Figure 12: Recursive OLAP query using Trino

Business Impact

By identifying missing data in billing and order records, OTE Group can reduce billing errors and prevent revenue losses. Strengthening data governance and compliance ensures that network deployment records remain complete and auditable. Improved collaboration between network providers and internal teams allows for more efficient issue resolution.

Furthermore, preventing delays in customer service and network provisioning enhances overall operational efficiency. This approach ensures that OTE Group operates with a data-driven strategy, reducing risk, increasing efficiency, and maintaining compliance with regulatory frameworks.

Visual and Strategic dimension scenario

Business Context

Building on the insights derived from the query depicted in Figure 12, in the context of the previous scenario, this evaluation shifts the focus towards metadata exploration and visualisation. The

query has already established patterns in missing billing and order data across different network providers, highlighting inconsistencies in infrastructure records. Now, the emphasis is on leveraging metadata to provide data analysts with actionable insights by structuring the extracted information into a new data product.

The effectiveness of network management depends not only on raw query results but also on the ability to interpret and contextualise this data within an analytical framework. By developing a metadata-driven data product, analysts can gain a structured, abstracted view of data quality issues, enabling them to detect systemic trends, root causes of inconsistencies, and the overall impact on operations.

A key enhancement in this scenario is the introduction of a metadata visualisation layer (Figure 13), allowing analysts to perform real-time exploratory analysis. This layer provides a visual representation of data completeness metrics, highlighting missing values across providers and regions. Instead of manually inspecting datasets, analysts can now interactively explore the metadata to identify problematic records and refine data governance strategies accordingly.

Figure 13: Metadata visualization layer

The objective of the Evaluation

The primary objective of this evaluation scenario is to transform the query results from the previous scenario into a metadata-driven analytical framework that enhances the interpretability of the findings. Instead of presenting missing records in raw tabular format, this approach introduces metadata tagging, categorisation, and visualisation, allowing for a more structured and efficient analysis process.

By leveraging this new metadata-enhanced data product, analysts can:

- Identify data quality issues across different network providers through an interactive dashboard.
- Explore missing values in billing and order tracking through metadata summaries rather than row-by-row inspections.
- Assess provider-specific data inconsistencies over time, identifying recurring gaps and ensuring accountability.
- Analyse deployment trends for network infrastructure based on metadata attributes such as region, provider, and historical completeness rates.

One of the key capabilities of this metadata-driven approach is that analysts can filter and drill down into specific aspects of the dataset in real-time. For example, if missing order data is disproportionately high for Huawei's equipment in the Attica region, analysts can correlate this pattern with external operational factors, such as provider-specific reporting practices, internal data entry processes, or system integration errors.

Furthermore, the new metadata layer supports ad hoc analysis, enabling business and technical users to customize their data exploration based on organizational priorities. Instead of relying on predefined reports, analysts can now dynamically investigate data inconsistencies, refine validation rules, and proactively suggest corrective actions.

Business Impact

By integrating metadata-driven insights into the data governance process, OTE Group can significantly enhance the efficiency of data analysis, anomaly detection, and operational decision-making. Instead of manually sifting through large datasets to locate missing records, analysts can now instantly visualize gaps and trends, leading to faster issue resolution and improved data quality.

From a financial perspective, ensuring that billing records are complete prevents revenue leakage caused by missing transactions. Similarly, improving order data accuracy ensures that network deployments are efficiently executed, reducing customer service delays, and enhancing overall satisfaction.

On an operational level, this approach fosters closer collaboration between data analysts, engineers, and network providers. By systematically identifying vendors with recurring data quality issues, OTE Group can enforce stricter data validation requirements for providers that repeatedly fail to maintain accurate records. This leads to stronger compliance with contractual obligations and ensures that infrastructure investments are properly documented.

From a strategic standpoint, the ability to interactively explore metadata, elevates data-driven decision-making across the organisation. Senior analysts and architects can now prioritise which datasets and departments need immediate intervention, ensuring that resources are allocated to the areas with the greatest impact on revenue, compliance, and service quality.

By shifting from static reporting to metadata-driven analytics, OTE Group gains the agility to proactively address data governance challenges, reducing the risk of regulatory fines, operational inefficiencies, and revenue losses. This transformation ensures that OTE Group remains competitive and adaptable in an era where real-time insights and data integrity are essential for sustainable telecom operations.

OLTP dimension scenario

Business Context

Customer retention is a critical factor for OTE Group to maintain revenue stability and customer satisfaction. Customers who pay high monthly bills and subscribe to multiple services provided by OTE, such as fixed & mobile telephony, subscription TV, electronic payment, and insurance services among other, represent a significant portion of the company's revenue. However, a common challenge arises when these high-value customers approach the end of their contracts without renewal efforts being proactively initiated. If these customers feel neglected or dissatisfied, they may opt to switch to a competitor, leading to revenue loss and higher acquisition costs for new customers.

OTE Group must identify customers at risk of leaving, particularly those whose contracts will expire in less than 15 days or who have not renewed within the past two months. Additionally, tracking multi-service customers ensures that those who have invested more in OTE's ecosystem receive personalized retention strategies. A metadata-driven approach is necessary to analyse

customer contract statuses, spending behaviour, and subscription engagement to facilitate proactive outreach before customer dissatisfaction increases a lot. By embedding this metadata analysis into the framework, analysts will have a real-time view of at-risk customers and can take immediate action to maintain customer loyalty.

A new data product can be created to identify customers at risk of leaving, enabling to download a targeted list that can be then forwarded to a dedicated retention team or an external contractor (Figure 14). This team will work to address any concerns and implement strategies to retain these customers within the organization.

Download Data Product [X]

Title

Telecommunication data 2025

Choose file format:

CSV [v]

CSV

json

xlsx

Download

Figure 14: Data Product creation

Designed with built-in security and privacy compliance, this data product adheres to the framework's regulatory standards, ensuring that all customer information is handled securely. The list can be downloaded or stored directly on the framework, allowing seamless distribution to the appropriate teams for immediate action while maintaining strict data governance protocols.

The objective of the Evaluation

This scenario focuses on identifying high-paying customers at risk of contract termination and flagging them for engagement. By leveraging metadata exploration and automated categorization, the framework allows analysts to detect which customers require immediate attention and prioritize outreach accordingly. The evaluation seeks to determine:

- Which high-value customers have contracts expiring within 15 days or have already expired within the last two months.
- Which customers are subscribed to multiple OTE services, making them more valuable and requiring additional retention efforts.
- Which customers have loyalty indicators, such as long-term subscriptions, yet show signs of potential disengagement.

This analysis will be conducted through a recursive OLTP query, dynamically identifying at-risk customers, and updating an engagement table to trigger personalized retention campaigns. Analysts will have the ability to filter customers by risk level, spending behaviour, and multi-service engagement using an interactive metadata dashboard. The real-time capabilities of this framework eliminate the need for manual data audits and provide customer success teams with instant insights into which customers need outreach the most.

By integrating metadata-driven contract tracking, the company ensures that no high-value customer is left unmanaged. Rather than waiting for customers to reach out with complaints or contract expiration issues, OTE Group can proactively reach out with personalized renewal offers, loyalty incentives, and service enhancements. This ensures that customers feel valued, increasing long-term engagement with OTE services.

Business Impact

By utilising metadata analysis to drive customer retention strategies, OTE Group can increase revenue, strengthen customer loyalty, and improve overall satisfaction. High-paying customers who feel valued through proactive renewal offers and personalized engagement are far less likely to consider alternative service providers. This ensures that premium customers continue their contracts, stabilizing OTE's recurring revenue streams.

Operational efficiency is also improved, as the customer success team can prioritize outreach based on metadata-driven risk levels, ensuring that the most valuable and time-sensitive cases receive immediate attention. The automation of customer risk detection eliminates the need for

manual contract reviews, allowing analysts to spend more time strategizing and optimizing customer interactions rather than searching for expiring contracts.

From a strategic standpoint, this approach shifts OTE Group from reactive customer service to proactive customer retention, ensuring that contracts are renewed well before expiration dates, reducing the risk of last-minute negotiations or customer frustration. Additionally, multi-service customers who have invested in OTE's ecosystem will be recognized and rewarded, strengthening brand loyalty, and making them less susceptible to competitive offers.

4.2.5. Feedback for improving design

During the pilot 2 test campaign, the following feedback has been provided to the technical partners:

Data Product Composition enriched functionalities

Based on the requirements defined in Pilot 2, the functionalities offered by the Data Product Composition module have been extended. In more detail, it has been enriched to be able to handle data not only coming from static files but also querying heterogeneous databases exploiting Trino tool capabilities.

User Defined Rules Generation improvements

The first version of the UDRG module needs further development to entirely fulfil pilot 2 requirements. For that reason, during a code camp session that took place in the context of the Aachen plenary meeting, we provided complex business quality rules based on the testing datasets. Those rules have been taken into consideration to further develop and improve the UDRG module.

4.2.6. Performance and usability of the DATAMITE framework

The KPIs defined for Pilot 2 are depicted in Table 3.

KPI	Description	Baseline	Target
KP1 - Query Clearance Time Reduction	Reduction in delays caused by manual approvals for data queries	Manual multi-level approvals causing long delays	Automated validation reducing time by 40%

KPI	Description	Baseline	Target
KP2 - Compliance-Ready Product Construction	Acceleration in the construction of compliance-ready data products	Manual efforts needed to align with EU regulations	Automated tagging accelerating process by 200%
KP3 - Query Execution Time Improvement	Improvement in execution time for queries across multiple databases	Custom integrations and manual mappings required	Optimized federated queries improving time by 12%
KP4 - Interoperability with EU Digital Commons	Increase in interoperability with EU digital infrastructure	Limited standard API connections and complex reuse	Automated metadata alignment increasing interoperability by 45%
KP5 - Regulatory Compliance and Sovereignty	Enhancement of data security and compliance monitoring	Manual data access reviews and compliance risks	Homomorphic encryption and AI monitoring increasing security by 35%
KP6 - Data Duplication Reduction	Reduction in excessive data duplication across repositories	Three instances per data source	Single authoritative source reducing infrastructure overhead
KP7 - Time to Market for New Data Products	Reduction in time required to prepare and launch new data products	Three to four weeks	Reduced to one week through automation and AI-driven checks

Table 3: Pilot 2 KPIs

The initial results of the DATAMITE framework demonstrate a significant breakthrough in governance, compliance, and workflow management (Figure 15), particularly in addressing the bureaucratic inefficiencies that large enterprises and organizations struggle with (Table 3). Traditional data management models often introduce delays, redundant approvals, and compliance bottlenecks, making it difficult for businesses to efficiently access, share, and monetise their data. However, with automated compliance validation, policy-based access

controls, and streamlined data governance, the new approach effectively tackles those challenges.

Figure 15: Performance spider

The DATAMITE framework significantly enhances data governance, security, and operational efficiency compared to legacy data management solutions. One of the most impactful improvements is in query clearance time, which has been reduced by 40%. Previously, organisations had to go through multiple levels of manual approvals before running queries on sensitive datasets. With DATAMITE’s automated compliance validation and policy-based access controls, analysts can execute queries faster, reducing delays in business intelligence and decision-making processes.

Furthermore, a critical improvement is the 200% acceleration in compliance-ready product construction. Traditional data governance models required extensive manual efforts to align datasets with EU Data Space regulations. DATAMITE framework automates regulatory tagging,

metadata standardisation, and interoperability validation, enabling organisations to create compliant data products in a fraction of the time. This ensures that data monetisation strategies are executed efficiently without the risk of regulatory non-compliance.

Moreover, the 12% reduction in query execution time across multiple databases further enhances data accessibility and operational speed. Legacy systems struggled with cross-platform queries, often requiring custom integrations and manual data mappings. DATAMITE framework optimizes federated queries and semantic caching, allowing organizations to retrieve insights faster while minimizing infrastructure costs.

Interoperability with EU Digital Commons has also improved by 45%, ensuring that datasets are easily integrated, shared, and monetised across European digital infrastructures such as EOSC (European Open Science Cloud). Previous models often lacked standardized API connections, making data reuse complex. DATAMITE introduces automated metadata alignment and compliance-driven data-sharing workflows, making it easier for businesses to participate in the European data economy.

In addition, regulatory compliance and sovereignty have been significantly strengthened, with a 35% increase. This is achieved through homomorphic encryption, differential privacy, and federated learning, ensuring that data remains protected even when shared across entities. Compared to older systems that relied on manual data access reviews, DATAMITE framework offers continuous monitoring and policy enforcement, reducing the risk of data breaches and compliance violations.

Another key enhancement introduced by the DATAMITE framework is the elimination of excessive data duplication, which has been reduced from three instances per data source to a maximum of one per data repository. In traditional models, multiple copies of the same data were often stored across different platforms, leading to increased storage costs, data inconsistencies, and version control issues. DATAMITE enforces centralised metadata governance and deduplication mechanisms, ensuring that each dataset is maintained in a single authoritative source, improving data integrity, and reducing infrastructure overhead.

Finally, the time to market for new data products has been significantly improved, dropping from an average of three to four weeks to just one week. Legacy systems often require lengthy manual processes to prepare, validate, and integrate data before launching new services or insights. With automated data onboarding, AI-driven compliance checks, and self-service analytics, DATAMITE

accelerates data preparation, validation, and sharing, enabling businesses to respond to market demands faster and gain a competitive advantage in monetising their data assets.

4.3. Pilot 3 - Offering Data to Service Providers with Data Spaces

System planning is a critical task for Distribution System Operators (DSOs) like HEDNO. It implies developing toolsets for the distribution network planning, aimed at delivering optimal decision support, optimising investments, and minimizing CAPEX & OPEX, taking under consideration the projected penetration of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) and stochastic loads (e.g., EVs) – considering smart charging services availability, grid constraints regarding losses, power factor, or voltage magnitudes. The following three modules may aid a DSO in planning better its system: a) optimal sizing/siting methodology to select and size the relevant assets (including RES, voltage regulators, etc.); b) AI-based load and Distributed Energy Resources (DERs) generation forecasts module; and c) AI-based state estimation algorithms to identify the state variables of the power system, while tackling low real-time data availability. To perform these tasks, an energy services provider may require and consume data from a DSO through Energy Data Spaces. In the frame of the pilot, pilot partner CERTH will act as the energy service provider, consuming the provided data to deliver its energy services back to the data provider, HEDNO. Specifically, HEDNO will provide a complex data product to CERTH, enabling it to simulate the operation of a section of HEDNO's medium-voltage (MV) network and propose optimization measures.

Currently, HEDNO collects and certifies measurements from its system, ensuring the availability and statistical analysis of metering data in accordance with data transparency principles and the protection of consumers' personal information. HEDNO uses Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI) Meter Data Management (MDM) systems to collect energy measurements. Sharing data with service providers is far from being an easy or automated process. Automation requires services to better find and manage data; to homogenise it; including semantic layers to minimize frictions between systems and increase data interoperability; to guarantee that sensitive and personal data is handled according to laws and regulations, including (pseudo-) anonymisation processes; or to define and enforce global data access control policies. This lack of automation not only complicates sharing data with service providers but also exploring monetisation or collaboration options like the exploitation of data markets or data spaces.

HEDNO will integrate DATAMITE to streamline the data sharing process across its various modules, ensuring that all data meets the required quality standards. Initially, the *Data Support Tools* will be used to discover data from HEDNO's databases used for SCADA and AMI data, and

to upload network topology files. Any sensitive information will be anonymized, the data will be harmonised, and finally securely stored in DATAMITE's storage service. Next, the *Data Quality* module will be employed to apply key performance indicators (KPIs) and user-defined quality rules established by HEDNO, ensuring that the data meets the necessary quality criteria for sharing with third parties. The metadata extracted from both the *Data Support Tools* and the *Data Quality* module will then be fed into the *Data Governance* module. This module will manage the lineage and versioning of the data, and, most importantly, will ensure seamless intra-corporate findability and accessibility of the data. Following this, the *Data Sharing* module will serve as the primary tool for onboarding HEDNO to IDSA/Gaia-X compliant dataspace and publishing data products. It will facilitate the creation of data products, and the assignment and enforcement of precise usage policies to them. Pilot 3's goal is to share these data products through Energy Data Spaces for broader dissemination to Energy Service Providers. A potential data consumer will find the products of interest in the catalogue, and, using the DATAMITE tools and Eclipse Dataspace Components (EDC) connector, will access and consume the products, offering new services. Finally, the *Data Security* module will define fine-grained access control for both the framework and the datasets, while also defining and assigning usage policies on the data products. Figure 16 illustrates the high-level architecture of Pilot 3 using data spaces.

In order to implement Pilot 3's objectives, a thorough demonstration and validation plan was designed that will employ all previously mentioned DATAMITE components in two testing iterations. Each iteration covers a specific aspect of the data exchange procedure and associated DATAMITE components, initially focusing on module integration, data preparation and ingestion, and finally facilitating the exchange of data products and services through data space. A series of scenarios utilising the various necessary components for Pilot 3, described in detail below, will be tested in each iteration. Feedback from the first iteration will be incorporated in the second, enhancing the usability and features of the components according to workflow demands and ensuring their quality and applicability.

Figure 16 High-level overview of Pilot 3.

4.3.1. Test Scenarios

4.3.1.1. Scenario 1 (Iteration 1): Dataset creation from multiple data sources

Components: *Data Discovery Tools, Data Ingestion & Storage, Data Governance Backend, Metadata Repository*

In this scenario, the process of discovering and ingesting data from multiple data sources is demonstrated. The data sources include PostgreSQL databases and an AWS S3 object storage service. Specifically, using the connectors provided by the *Data Discovery Tools*, the DATAMITE framework connects directly to the following systems:

- A replica PostgreSQL database that collects measurement data from the SCADA system.
- A replica PostgreSQL database of the Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI) Meter Data Management (MDM) system, which receives measurement data for all medium-voltage consumers/producers, validates them and distributes them to the energy providers

- A replica S3-compatible storage service that is used as a repository for medium-voltage network model files in PowerFactory¹ format.

In addition to the above, the demonstration includes bulk uploading CSV files from the first two data sources, as well as PowerFactory network model files. These files are ingested and stored within the storage mechanism of the *Data Ingestion & Storage* component.

For each of these cases, datasets are created, and the user provides metadata information, such as descriptions, domains, glossary terms (Figure 17), and grants access permissions. Once the process is successfully completed, the datasets appear in the *Data Catalogue* (Figure 18). They include their schemas (Figure 19), the associated metadata provided by the user, and their corresponding access permissions.

The screenshot shows a dark-themed web interface for creating a dataset. It is divided into two main sections:

- 1. Dataset name:** A large rounded rectangle containing the text "SCADA MS-Location1 Database".
- 2. Fill in with the Basic Info:** This section contains several sub-sections:
 - Full description:** A text area with the content: "The SCADA Database contains measurements covering data concerning the MS-Location1 HV/MV substation. The measurements include: voltage measurements, b) line load mea".
 - Short description:** A text area with the content: "The SCADA Database contains SCADA measurements from MS-Location1 HV/MV substation, including semi-bar voltages, loads of MV lines, and active/reactive power."
 - Domains:** A search bar with a magnifying glass icon and a single tag labeled "Energy".
 - Glossary/Terms:** Two expandable sections. The first, "SCADA Measurements⁷", is expanded to show tags: "Remote Terminal Unit", "Transformer", "High Voltage", "Semi-bar", and "Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition" (with a "+ 2" and a dropdown arrow). The second, "SCADA Powers²", is collapsed and shows tags: "Reactive power" and "Active power".

Figure 17: Adding metadata and associating to glossary terms of a new dataset

¹ PowerFactory - DlgSILENT

Figure 18: Overview of the *Data Catalogue*.

Figure 19: Database schema extracted by the *Data Discovery Tools*

4.3.1.2. Scenario 2 (Iteration 1): Data product composition with anonymised data

Components: *Data Product Composition, Data Ingestion & Storage, Data Anonymisation, Data Governance Backend, Metadata Repository*

This scenario demonstrates the creation of a data product using the *Data Product Composition* component. The process uses datasets generated from multiple bulk-uploaded files originating from all three data sources. A synthetic data product is created by combining CSV files from the SCADA system, CSV files from the AMI (Advanced Metering Infrastructure), and a PowerFactory file that holds the network topology of the corresponding medium-voltage (MV) lines, for which the aforementioned SCADA and AMI measurements are provided.

The composition process includes anonymising sensitive data columns contained in the AMI datasets, by utilising the anonymisation capabilities of the *Data Anonymisation* component (Figure 20), removing columns that are not mandatory for the final data product, analysing and merging structured files that can be unified (Figure 21), and bundling the composite data product with the inclusion of the binary semi-structured PowerFactory files.

Additionally, a data product is created directly from the PostgreSQL database of the *Telemetry Center*. This involves executing queries on the database using the Trino SQL query engine (Figure 20 - Figure 22), which is integrated in the *Data Product Composition* component, and applying anonymisation techniques to sensitive data, as is done for the composite data product. These steps showcase how structured, semi-structured, and sensitive data from diverse sources are processed, anonymised, and combined into meaningful data products.

Figure 20: Selection of sensitive columns (left). Suggestion of anonymisation techniques (right).

Figure 21: Deletion of specific columns and aggregation per row of multiple files.

Pending approval by the EC

Get all SCADA voltage measurements
✕

Id

Is Recursive

Is Deleted

Name

Query Result

Timestamp

Query

```
SELECT s.hv_mv substation, s.transformer, s.bar, s.semibar, s.scada_time,
s.source_time,
s.label,
s.description,
s.value,
s.unit
FROM hed s
```

Notes

The SCADA dataset contains semi-bar voltage measurements of one whole year's data concerning an HV/MV substation.

Result

source_time	label	description	value	unit
00:46.000 2022-01-01 03:00:46.000	MS-Location1_Semi-bar_1-1	20KV SEMI-BAR 1-1 VOLTAGE	21148.27	V
45:47.000 2022-01-01 11:45:47.000	MS-Location1_Semi-bar_1-1	20KV SEMI-BAR 1-1 VOLTAGE	20941.37	V
30:47.000 2022-01-01 12:30:47.000	MS-Location1_Semi-bar_1-1	20KV SEMI-BAR 1-1 VOLTAGE	20940.07	V
45:47.000 2022-01-01 12:45:47.000	MS-Location1_Semi-bar_1-1	20KV SEMI-BAR 1-1 VOLTAGE	20928.14	V
00:51.000 2022-01-01 23:00:51.000	MS-Location1_Semi-bar_1-1	20KV SEMI-BAR 1-1 VOLTAGE	21272.22	V

Figure 22: Execution of query directly to PostgreSQL using Trino query engine.

4.3.1.3. Scenario 3 (Iteration 2): Data quality assessment with user-defined rules

Components: *User Defined Rules Generator, Quality Evaluator, KPI Library, Data Governance Backend, Metadata Repository, Data Discovery Tools, Access Control*

This scenario will involve the definition of user-defined rules as well as their application in existing data products to improve their quality. These rules will include value filtering, checks for incorrect values, as well as guarantees for data completeness. Through these rules, assurance will be provided that the final product conforms to modern data standards and is ready for use by consumers.

Through the *User Defined Rules Generator* (UDRG) component, a set of quality rules will be defined and applied to datasets. The *Quality Evaluator* will then evaluate the user-defined rules combined with pre-defined indicators, provided by the *KPI Library*, ensuring the quality of the data product.

4.3.1.4. Scenario 4 (Iteration 2): Definition of access/usage policies

Components: *Data Sovereignty, Access Control*

This scenario concerns a crucial step before publication of a data product. Once a data product has been successfully created and verified (Scenarios 1 – 3), all relevant access and usage policies need to be defined. These policies, offered by the *Policy Library* within the *Data Sovereignty* component control data access/usage by external parties (e.g., time-based access). A user can read the access policy for each data product, ensuring transparency between the involved parties. The access/usage policies will be enforced by the EDC connector, which also monitors data usage, guaranteeing data safety and compliance with each policy.

Policies are defined and managed through the user interface, where a data product is selected from the catalogue. Following, the user fills a template by adding information about the defined policy in the relevant fields (e.g., name of policy), and completes the definition by setting permission rules (e.g., time-based access) according to company requirements and specifications. The newly created policy is then applied to the data product.

4.3.1.5. Scenario 5 (Iteration 2): Data product composition with harmonised data

Components: *Data Product Composition, Data Ingestion & Storage, Data Harmonisation, Data Governance Backend, Metadata Repository, Data Lineage, Data Versioning, Access Control*

In this scenario, a composite data product bundle using all three data sources is created. Similar to Scenario 2, datasets from HEDNO's infrastructure are used to compose a data product. Due to the different nature of the data sources, the *Data Harmonisation* component is employed to alleviate mismatches of their structures by aligning them to a common format, allowing their usage by other DATAMITE modules and components. More specifically, a reference is defined alongside vocabularies that together constitute a topology similar to a database schema. This topology guides the data transformations during the harmonisation process.

A series of steps are involved in each dataset. First, meta-data (e.g., field names, data types) is extracted from the datasets. Then, the meta-data alongside the reference model and vocabularies are used to construct mapping rules that are necessary to transform the data from the original to

the target structure. Finally, the data transformation takes place producing a harmonised data product that expresses the original data according to the terms of the reference model, specified by the mapping rules.

4.3.1.6. Scenario 6 (Iteration 2): Onboarding procedure to an Energy Data Space

Components: *IDSA & Gaia-X Components, Access Control*

Onboarding is the process of issuing the required credentials for new participants to access a Data Space, ensuring compliance, and enabling secure data exchange. The process results in the generation of a Participant Verifiable Presentation (VP) through services provided by a Gaia-X Digital Clearing House (GXDCH), specifically the Registry Service, and Notary Service (explained in technical detail in deliverable D2.1). The Participant VP serves as a self-description of HEDNO's pilot, certifying its compliance with Gaia-X security specifications and rules, and verifies that the participant is indeed HEDNO. It also allows HEDNO to access an Energy Data Space that is compliant to Gaia-X. The interaction with the GXDCH is fully automated and handled by the IDSA and Gaia-X Components, provided an [X.509](#) security certificate has been issued for the HEDNO's subdomain that is used to host Pilot 3 by a [Trust Anchor](#).

The onboarding process involves several steps. First, the details of the pilot and HEDNO are entered, including the domain of the pilot and legal information of the company. Next, a decentralized identifier is created based on the domain and the X.509 certificate []. Finally, the Participant VP is issued by the GXDCH's services and stored locally within the *IDSA & Gaia-X Components*.

4.3.1.7. Scenario 7 (Iteration 2): Data product publishing to Energy Data Space Catalogue

Components: *IDSA & Gaia-X Components, Data Product Composition, Logging, Access Control*

To make the created products findable and accessible by a consumer and to facilitate data offering with a data space, in this scenario we will publish a data product's metadata to an Energy Data Space's Catalogue, such as DATA CELLAR² or Omega-X³. This process requires the existence of a Participant Verifiable Presentation (VP), and access to the provided services of a

² [DATA CELLAR PROJECT](#)

³ [Omega-X – Orchestrating an interoperable sovereign federated Multi-vector Energy Data Space built on open standards and ready for GAia-X](#)

Gaia-X Digital Clearing House (GXDCH), specifically the Registry Service, Compliance Service, and Credential Event Service (explained in technical detail in deliverable D2.1), both by HEDNO and by the Energy Data Space's Catalogue.

The process begins with selecting a data product for sharing. Next, additional information required for sharing through a data space and is missing by data product's metadata is entered, such as licensing and copyright details. Once the information is verified as correct and a valid Participant VP, a Data Product VP is generated with the assistance of GXDCH Registry Service. The Data Product VP then undergoes a compliance check using the GXDCH Compliance Service, and upon validation, the metadata of the complete data product is published to the Credential Event Service of the GXDCH.

From there, the Energy Data Space's Catalogue gains access to the data product metadata for potential consumers to browse.

4.3.1.8. Scenario 8 (Iteration 2): Data product search and consumption via Energy Data Space

Components: *IDSA & Gaia-X Components, Data Product Composition, Data Ingestion & Storage, Logging*

This scenario concludes Pilot 3's demonstration plan by facilitating a data exchange procedure between the data provider HEDNO and the data consumer CERTH. This scenario requires both participants to have valid Participant Verifiable Presentations (VP), issued by the Energy Data Space's Gaia-X Digital Clearing House (GXDCH), and the successful completion of all previous scenarios, as all steps involved are essential in the data exchange. At this point, a data product's metadata should have been published in the Energy Data Space Catalogue. CERTH will browse the Catalogue and perform a (meta-data) search for relevant keywords. Then, CERTH will review the access/usage policy, the license, and the copyright terms, and finally, a data contract negotiation with HEDNO will be initiated. If the data contract is successful, CERTH will be able to download the files. The Eclipse Dataspace Components (EDC) connector is used for the data exchange, enforcing the access/usage policy associated with the data product and ensuring that the data consumer meets the policy requirements.

4.3.2. Solution implementation

The pilot architecture is shown in Figure 23.

rules by the *User Defined Rules Generator*. These components offer a solution for data quality profiling, making it easy to automate and integrate quality checks into data pipelines, and help the data provider to improve, ensure or enhance the quality of the data. The quality analysis metadata is then fed into the *Data Governance* module.

Both the metadata from the *Data Discovery Tools* describing the datasets and the evaluation results from the Quality Evaluator are provided to the *Data Governance Backend*, which is the core and most crucial component of the *Data Governance* module. The *Data Governance Backend* stores all metadata to the *Metadata Repository*, while keeping track of the history and the changes of the datasets using the *Data Versioning* and the *Data Lineage* components. It is also responsible for providing all this metadata information to the front-end and to the *Data Sharing* module.

The *Data Security* module encompasses a comprehensive set of security features, from which we retain the *Data Sovereignty* and the *Access Control* components. The former is used for the definition of data access and usage policies, while the latter provides security by granting access and authorizing users to the data and the DATAMITE modules.

The final part of the pipeline pertains to the *Data Sharing* module, where Pilot 3 will utilise the *Data Product Composition* component, the *IDSA & Gaia-X Components* and the *Logging* component. The *Data Product Composition* takes on the task of gathering data from the data sources (either HEDNO's *Internal Systems* or the *Data Ingestion & Storage* component), and combining them into one composite bundle, the data product. The corresponding metadata of the datasets are retrieved from the *Data Governance Backend* and the data product flows through the components of *Data Support Tools*.

Subsequently, the *Data Anonymisation* tool transforms all sensitive information, and the *Data Harmonisation* tool creates the final composite, homogeneous dataset. The *Data Ingestion & Storage* component will be utilised for storing the initial and the updated versions (harmonised and anonymised) of the data product.

Furthermore, the *Data Product Composition* retrieves the definitions of the data access/usage policies from the *Data Sovereignty* component, and forwards them, along with the relative data products, to the *IDSA & Gaia-X Components*.

IDSA & Gaia-X Components is the main component responsible for publishing the data to the Data Space, and for safeguarding data sovereignty throughout the entire data-sharing process. In particular, it will be used for onboarding HEDNO to a Data Space, sharing the data products'

metadata to federated catalogues, facilitating communication between the data provider and the consumers using the Eclipse Dataspace Components (EDC) Connector, and, ultimately, for enforcing the access/usage policies which are defined and retrieved from the *Data Sovereignty* component.

Finally, the *Logging* component will be used for recording and logging the details of the data sharing process.

The pilot's architecture is illustrated in Figure 23, and all the components described above are outlined in Table 4.

Data Governance	Data Quality	Data Security	Data Sharing	Data Support Tools
Metadata Repository ^{1,2}	Quality Evaluator ²	Data Sovereignty ²	IDSA & Gaia-X Connectors & Components ²	Data Discovery Tools ¹
Data Versioning ²	KPI Library ²	Access Control ²	Data Product Composition ^{1,2}	Data Ingestion & Storage ^{1,2}
Data Lineage ²	User Defined Rules Generator ²		Logging ²	Data Harmonisation ²
Data Governance Backend ¹				Data Anonymisation ¹
1: Component tested at iteration 1				
2: Component tested at iteration 2				

Table 4: DATAMITE components utilised for Pilot 3.

4.3.2.1. Datasets

In Pilot 3, HEDNO will provide a complex data product to energy provider CERTH, that will allow the latter to run a simulation of the operation of a part of HEDNO's MV network and offer optimisation propositions.

This data product will be composed of the following three distinct, but interconnected datasets, concerning the network model and measurements of chosen MV lines departing from an HV/MV Substation:

- Model of the MV network departing from a HV/MV substation that is part of the interconnected continental grid
- SCADA measurements of relative bars and lines of the provided MV network
- AMI (Advanced Metering Infrastructure) measurements collected from the smart meters of MV consumers and MV producers connected to the same lines

Network model files

The model of the Medium Voltage (MV) network that is being electrified by an HV/MV substation with its topology and its electric parameters will be provided in a PowerFactory file (see Figure). In the aforementioned figure, the picture on the left depicts MV consumers of one MV line departing from this HV/MV substation, while the picture on the right holds the electrical diagram of one of these MV clients. The HV/MV substation is part of the Greek interconnected continental grid, (i.e., it is not a substation residing on one the non-interconnected Greek islands). This substation consists of 2 separate HV/MV transformers, each electrifying one of two separate semi-bars, which can be conjunct together in the case of an event (e.g., power failure), but during normal operation this conjunction is normally open. Each transformer has a nominal apparent value of $S = 50$ MVA. The high-voltage lines that feed the HV/MV transformers operate at 400 KV, while the medium-voltage lines departing from the semi-bars operate at 20 KV.

Figure 24: Network topology sample from PowerFactory file.

SCADA Dataset

The SCADA dataset contains measurements covering one whole year's SCADA partial data concerning the HV/MV substation, which is given in the network model file.

The measurements include semi-bar voltages, loads of chosen MV lines, as well as active and reactive power measurements. The dataset is organised in three database tables, one for each type of measurement. Their structure is provided in the following Tables (Table 5, Table 6, Table 7). Samples of the datasets are illustrated in screenshot format in Figures Figure 25 - Figure 27.

Table	voltage_measurements	
Description	Voltage measurements of one semi-bar associated with a specific bar and transformer within one location.	
Schema		
Column	Type	Description
hv_mv_substation	character varying (20)	High/Medium voltage substation where measurements are obtained from
transformer	character varying (10)	Transformer ID
bar	character varying (5)	Associated bar ID
semibar	character varying (5)	Associated semi-bar ID
scada_time	timestamp	Timestamp of the moment that the measurement is saved in the SCADA server
source_time	timestamp	Timestamp of measurement as logged in the RTU of the measurement device
label	character varying (35)	Description about the location and associated semi-bar ID
description	character varying (35)	Description about the measurement type, containing the semi-bar ID
value	double precision	Value of the measurement, e.g., 20100.10
unit	character varying (1)	Measurement unit (Volts)

Table 5: Structure of the voltage measurements database table, part of the SCADA dataset.

HV/MV substation	Transformer	Bar	Semibar	SCADA time	Source time	Label	Description	Value	Unit
	MS-1	1	1-1	2022-02-02 00:00:45	2022-02-02 00:00:45		20KV SEMI-BAR 1-1 VOLTAGE	20913.96	V
	MS-1	1	1-1	2022-02-02 03:15:46	2022-02-02 03:15:46		20KV SEMI-BAR 1-1 VOLTAGE	21092.78	V
	MS-1	1	1-1	2022-02-02 13:15:45	2022-02-02 13:15:45		20KV SEMI-BAR 1-1 VOLTAGE	21137.56	V
	MS-1	1	1-1	2022-02-02 14:00:46	2022-02-02 14:00:46		20KV SEMI-BAR 1-1 VOLTAGE	21279.39	V
	MS-1	1	1-1	2022-02-02 15:15:47	2022-02-02 15:15:47		20KV SEMI-BAR 1-1 VOLTAGE	21033.35	V
	MS-1	1	1-1	2022-02-02 20:45:47	2022-02-02 20:45:47		20KV SEMI-BAR 1-1 VOLTAGE	21074.04	V
	MS-1	1	1-1	2022-02-03 04:30:48	2022-02-03 04:30:48		20KV SEMI-BAR 1-1 VOLTAGE	21063.56	V
	MS-1	1	1-1	2022-02-03 09:15:49	2022-02-03 09:15:49		20KV SEMI-BAR 1-1 VOLTAGE	21007.36	V
	MS-1	1	1-1	2022-02-03 13:00:50	2022-02-03 13:00:50		20KV SEMI-BAR 1-1 VOLTAGE	21216.94	V
	MS-1	1	1-1	2022-02-03 16:15:50	2022-02-03 16:15:50		20KV SEMI-BAR 1-1 VOLTAGE	20933.04	V

Figure 25: Data sample of the voltage measurements table with sensitive information hidden.

Table	load_measurements	
Description	Line load measurements of one line associated with a specific bar, semi-bar and transformer within one location.	
Schema		
Column	Type	Description
hv_mv_substation	character varying (20)	High/Medium voltage substation where measurements are obtained from
transformer	character varying (10)	Transformer ID
bar	character varying (5)	Associated bar ID
semibar	character varying (5)	Associated semi-bar ID
line	character varying (10)	Associated consumer line ID
scada_time	timestamp	Timestamp of the moment that the measurement is saved in the SCADA server
source_time	timestamp	Timestamp of measurement as logged in the RTU of the measurement device
label	character varying (35)	Description about the location and associated line ID
description	character varying (35)	Description about the measurement type, containing the line ID
value	double precision	Value of the measurement, e.g., 14.05
unit	character varying (1)	Measurement unit (Amperes)

Table 6: Structure of the load measurements database table, part of the SCADA dataset.

HV/MV Substation	Transformer	Bar	Semi-Bar	Line	Scada time	Source time	Label	Description	Value	Unit
	MS-1	1	1-1	1-16	2022-12-31 22:00:21	2022-12-31 22:00:21		LINE 1-16 CURRENT	21.28	A
	MS-1	1	1-1	1-16	2022-12-31 22:30:22	2022-12-31 22:30:22		LINE 1-16 CURRENT	22.55	A
	MS-1	1	1-1	1-16	2022-12-31 23:00:23	2022-12-31 23:00:23		LINE 1-16 CURRENT	19.33	A
	MS-1	1	1-1	1-16	2022-12-31 23:30:22	2022-12-31 23:30:22		LINE 1-16 CURRENT	19.20	A
	MS-1	1	1-1	1-16	2022-12-31 23:45:22	2022-12-31 23:45:22		LINE 1-16 CURRENT	20.54	A
	MS-2	1	1-2	1-19	2022-01-01 00:00:43	2022-01-01 00:00:43		LINE 1-19 CURRENT (REVERSE FLOW)	9.42	A
	MS-2	1	1-2	1-19	2022-01-01 00:15:43	2022-01-01 00:15:43		LINE 1-19 CURRENT (REVERSE FLOW)	9.08	A
	MS-2	1	1-2	1-19	2022-01-01 00:30:43	2022-01-01 00:30:42		LINE 1-19 CURRENT (REVERSE FLOW)	10.09	A
	MS-2	1	1-2	1-19	2022-01-01 00:45:42	2022-01-01 00:45:42		LINE 1-19 CURRENT (REVERSE FLOW)	7.97	A
	MS-2	1	1-2	1-19	2022-01-01 01:00:43	2022-01-01 01:00:42		LINE 1-19 CURRENT (REVERSE FLOW)	9.25	A

Figure 26: Data sample of the load measurements table with sensitive information hidden.

Table		
Table	power_measurements	
Description		
Description	Power consumption measurements of one semi-bar associated with a specific bar and transformer within one location.	
Schema		
Column	Type	Description
hv_mv_substation	character varying (20)	High/Medium voltage substation where measurements are obtained from
transformer	character varying (10)	Transformer ID
bar	character varying (5)	Associated bar ID
semibar	character varying (5)	Associated semi-bar ID
scada_time	timestamp	Timestamp of the moment that the measurement is saved in the SCADA server
source_time	timestamp	Timestamp of measurement as logged in the RTU of the measurement device
label	character varying (20)	Description about the location, associated semi-bar ID and type of power measurement
description	character varying (30)	Description about the measurement type, containing the associated semi-bar and transformer
power_type	character varying (1)	Type of measurement (“P” and “Q” only)
value	double precision	Value of the measurement, e.g., -2.1, 15.25
unit	character varying (4)	Measurement unit (“MW” for measurements of “P”, “MVar” for measurements of “Q”)

Table 7: Structure of the power consumption measurements database table, part of the SCADA dataset.

HV/MV substation	Transformer	Bar	Semibar	Scada time	Source time	Label	Description	Power type	Value	Unit
	MS-1	1	1-1	2022-01-08 04:30:16	2022-01-08 04:30:15		Q - Semi-Bar 20 KV 1-1 M/S-1	Q	-3.20	MVAR
	MS-1	1	1-1	2022-01-08 05:45:15	2022-01-08 05:45:15		Q - Semi-Bar 20 KV 1-1 M/S-1	Q	-3.60	MVAR
	MS-1	1	1-1	2022-01-08 06:00:15	2022-01-08 06:00:14		Q - Semi-Bar 20 KV 1-1 M/S-1	Q	-3.31	MVAR
	MS-1	1	1-1	2022-01-08 06:00:15	2022-01-08 06:00:14		P - Semi-Bar 20 KV 1-1 M/S-1	P	15.10	MW
	MS-1	1	1-1	2022-01-08 07:30:16	2022-01-08 07:30:15		P - Semi-Bar 20 KV 1-1 M/S-1	P	15.70	MW
	MS-1	1	1-1	2022-01-08 07:45:16	2022-01-08 07:45:15		Q - Semi-Bar 20 KV 1-1 M/S-1	Q	-3.84	MVAR
	MS-1	1	1-1	2022-01-08 08:15:15	2022-01-08 08:15:15		Q - Semi-Bar 20 KV 1-1 M/S-1	Q	-3.77	MVAR
	MS-1	1	1-1	2022-01-08 08:15:15	2022-01-08 08:15:15		P - Semi-Bar 20 KV 1-1 M/S-1	P	17.03	MW
	MS-1	1	1-1	2022-01-08 09:15:15	2022-01-08 09:15:15		Q - Semi-Bar 20 KV 1-1 M/S-1	Q	-1.93	MVAR
	MS-1	1	1-1	2022-01-08 09:45:16	2022-01-08 09:45:15		Q - Semi-Bar 20 KV 1-1 M/S-1	Q	-2.99	MVAR

Figure 27: Data sample of the power measurements table with sensitive information hidden.

AMI Dataset

Similar to the SCADA dataset, the AMI dataset contains energy measurements for an entire year obtained from smart meters associated with the client's transformer and his supply number. These measurements include active and reactive energy measurements, measured in KWh and KVARh, respectively. The measurement interval is 15 minutes, meaning that there are 100 measurements per day, with 96 values being typical. The extra 4 measurements cover the case where a day has 25 hours due to Daylight Savings Time. This dataset is organized in a single database table, with the following structure, as shown in Table 8. The sample data shown in Figure 28 below shows sensitive information blurred out and has measurement columns Q4 to Q97 hidden for demonstration purposes.

Table	ami_measurements	
Description	Smart meter measurements of one line.	
Schema		
Column	Type	Description
hv_mv_substation	character varying (20)	High/Medium voltage substation where measurements are obtained from
transformer	character varying (10)	Transformer ID
bar	character varying (5)	Associated bar ID
semibar	character varying (5)	Associated semi-bar ID
line	character varying (10)	Associated consumer line ID
supply_num	character varying (15)	Supply number ID
client_transformer	character varying (10)	Customer transformer ID where the smart meter is located
data_class	character varying (10)	Description about the measurement type

date_read	date	Date of measurement, in the MM/DD/YYYY format
q1 – q100	double precision	Energy measurement per quarter of an hour (15 minutes) for a day, unit depending on data_class

Table 8: Structure of the smart meter measurements database table, which comprises the AMI dataset.

HV_MV_SUBSTATION	TRANSFORMER	BAR	SEMIBAR	LINE	SUPPLY_NUM	CLIENT_TRANSFORMER	DATA_CLASS	DATE_READ	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q98	Q99	Q100
	MS-1	1	1-1	1-16			active+	9/19/2022	3.0	4.5	3.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	MS-1	1	1-1	1-16			active+	9/20/2022	3.0	3.0	3.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	MS-1	1	1-1	1-16			active+	9/21/2022	4.5	3.0	3.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	MS-1	1	1-1	1-16			active+	9/22/2022	3.0	3.0	3.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	MS-1	1	1-1	1-16			active+	9/23/2022	3.0	3.0	4.5	0.0	0.0	0.0
	MS-1	1	1-1	1-16			active+	9/1/2022	0.64	0.6	0.64	0.0	0.0	0.0
	MS-1	1	1-1	1-16			active+	9/2/2022	0.64	0.64	0.64	0.0	0.0	0.0
	MS-1	1	1-1	1-16			active+	9/3/2022	0.6	0.64	0.64	0.0	0.0	0.0
	MS-1	1	1-1	1-16			active+	9/4/2022	0.6	0.64	0.64	0.0	0.0	0.0
	MS-1	1	1-1	1-16			active+	9/5/2022	0.6	0.6	0.64	0.0	0.0	0.0

Figure 28: Data sample of the smart meter measurements database with sensitive information hidden.

4.3.3. Training Materials planned

Upon reaching an appropriate level of maturity during the second iteration of the Pilot demonstration, training materials will be developed. One course will be specifically designed for HEDNO employees, while a second course will target any interested potential users of data spaces.

Initially, a training course comprising explanatory text, demonstration videos, and evaluation questions will be developed to assist HEDNO employees, who are not involved with DATAMITE, in comprehending fundamental concepts of data spaces and understanding the capabilities of the DATAMITE framework tools. Upon completion of the course, learners are expected to evaluate DATAMITE's usefulness and potentially consider its integration into their business routines.

A second course aimed at energy stakeholders will introduce the concepts of data spaces and demonstrate the data sharing process through an energy data space, from both the provider's and consumer's perspectives.

4.3.4. Test Campaign

The demonstration and validation plan is divided into two iterations with deadlines set for February 28th, 2025 (M26) and October 31st, 2025 (M36). These iterations will cumulatively utilise all the components employed in Pilot 3. The objectives are implemented in 8 scenarios, with the first 2 scenarios included in the first iteration and the remaining 6 in the second iteration. Pilot 3's demonstration and validation plan is summarized in Table 9 and Table 10.

Iteration phase 1	
Description	The first iteration is focused on integrating the DATAMITE framework with HEDNO's internal systems, discovering and ingesting data, and extracting and storing the associated metadata. Additionally, it includes the creation of synthetic data products generated from various datasets originating from multiple sources. These data products will undergo anonymisation to protect sensitive information.
Scenarios	1 – 2
Timeline	M23 – M26

Table 9: Overview of the iteration phase 1

Iteration phase 2	
Description	The second iteration will focus on data quality and sharing. More specifically, data quality rules are defined and applied to evaluate the datasets, leveraging the built-in KPIs provided by the DATAMITE framework. Secondly, access and usage policies for the data products will be defined for data consumers. Furthermore, the onboarding process of the pilot into an Energy Data Space will be demonstrated. Finally, the demonstration concludes with a complete instance of a data exchange between two partners (a data provider and a consumer) using an Energy Data Space.
Scenarios	3 – 8
Timeline	M27 – M32

Table 10: Overview of the iteration phase 2.

The test scenarios will initially be executed and evaluated by HEDNO's DATAMITE team in cooperation with CERTH's DATAMITE team, where necessary. Upon successful completion and any necessary improvements in the described processes and tools, relevant training materials will be developed and distributed to targeted individuals within the company. Synchronous training sessions, including one-to-one sessions, will be organized based on feedback from colleagues. The pool of individuals engaged will primarily include employees from the Business Analytics & Data Management Department, researchers from the Research and Innovation Department, and other key users who share data with external stakeholders. The evaluation of the platform tools

and their integration into business processes will be complemented by a questionnaire, which will be distributed to the engaged employees for completion.

4.3.5. Feedback for improving design

Bundling of Composite Data Products Using the Data Product Composition Component

The full data product for Pilot 3 is synthesized from three distinct data sources, which, when combined, can be used for system planning. Two of these data sources contain structured, text-based data, while the third contains binary semi-structured files in the proprietary PowerFactory format. Due to the PowerFactory files, data from all three sources cannot be merged into a single structured file. For this reason, the support for bundling datasets into a zip file was requested and integrated into the *Data Product Composition* component.

Techniques for Anonymisation – Data Anonymisation

For the development of the *Data Anonymisation* component, we provided sample data to the developers and requested anonymisation capabilities to ensure that sensitive data included in the Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI) measurements is secure. Based on our feedback, the developers implemented anonymisation techniques tailored to our requirements.

Providing Requirements for the User Defined Rules Generator

During the development of the *User Defined Rules Generator*, we were asked to provide feedback on the format of the quality rules. The rules are designed as inequalities combined with the built-in KPIs of the *KPI Library*. We proposed using KPIs in both sides of the inequality, including the option to apply coefficients. This structure was integrated into the *User Defined Rules Generator*, enabling the definition of rules in this format.

Quality Evaluator – Bug Report

When uploading new data to the DATAMITE platform, the *Quality Evaluator* begins extracting basic metrics from the datasets. The *Quality Evaluator* invokes the *KPI Library* and the *User Defined Rules Generator*. However, in an earlier version of the demonstration infrastructure, the *User Defined Rules Generator* was not yet included in the pipelines. Theoretically, the extraction of basic metrics should depend solely on the *KPI Library*, as it does not involve the application of user-defined quality rules provided by the *User Defined Rules Generator*.

Due to a programming bug in the *Quality Evaluator*, this behaviour was not as expected, causing internal software exceptions. As a result, the basic metrics were not displayed in the Data Catalogue. After providing feedback to the developers, they managed to identify the issue, which

was resolved by incorporating the *User Defined Rules Generator* into the pipelines of the demonstration infrastructure project.

Integration of Data Product Composition with S3-Compatible Storage Services

HEDNO uses an S3-compatible storage service to store PowerFactory topology files. Currently, direct data retrieval from the S3-compatible storage service is not yet supported by the DATAMITE platform. Enabling this direct communication would be highly beneficial for Pilot 3's case. Depending on the framework's capabilities, we will adapt our infrastructure to ensure this communication is possible.

SSH Tunnelling

During the deployment of the demonstration infrastructure, we required access to the virtual machine (VM) through SSH tunnelling. Specifically, we used Local Port Forwarding to avoid exposing the necessary ports publicly during deployment, securely routing interactions with the server through a secure tunnel. However, the use of "localhost" complicates the internal pipelines of the demonstration infrastructure, as the server domain is used internally.

We communicated this issue to the developers of the demonstration infrastructure, requesting support for "localhost" usage to enable seamless Local Port Forwarding. This feature is currently under development.

4.3.6. Validation KPIs

The KPIs for validation of Pilot 3 are split in two iterations, following the test scenarios. Initially, the KPIs evaluated in the first iteration focus on the collection of data from several sources as well as the successful deployment of DATAMITE components to facilitate the demonstration of the test scenarios. In the current status of the pilot, these KPIs (KPIs 1 to 6 and KPI 8) have been achieved. By the end of the second iteration, the remaining KPIs will validate the performance and usability of the framework from a multi-dimensional approach covering complete deployment of the framework, achieving the exchange and exploitation of data products, and generating value for HEDNO from the business perspective through personnel upskilling and defining a procedure for using a data space for product sharing.

Detailed descriptions about the KPIs of Pilot 3's validation plan are provided in the following Table 11.

KPI	Description	Baseline	Target	Iteration
KPI1	Collection of Voltage, Current and Power Measurements, as well as the nominal values of MV/LV transformers of the provided grid	0	100% of the data needed for the simulation purposes of the system planning tools	1
KPI2	Data of the Active Power, Reactive Power, Energy Consumption (for consumers) and Energy Production (for producers)		≥ 1 MV consumer per 500kVA of installed apparent consumption power ≥ 1 MV producer per 250kVA installed apparent production power	1
KPI3	Network diagram (nodes and line data)	0	1	1
KPI4	Number of different datasets to be included	0	≥ 3	1
KPI5	Setup of dedicated VM for DATAMITE	0	≥ 1 (VM)	1
KPI6	Number of developed connectors compatible with internal system to be deployed	0	≥ 1	1
KPI7	Deployed DATAMITE modules	None	> 3 DATAMITE modules	2
KPI8	Datasets processed by Data Governance, Data Quality or Data Security modules	0	> 90% data involved in the Pilot	1
KPI9	Datasets processed with the involvement of Access Control and Data Sovereignty components	0	> 80% data involved in the Pilot	2
KPI10	On-boarding to a Gaia-X compliant data space	0	≥ 1 data space	2
KPI11	Energy Data Spaces used for data sharing	0	≥ 1 Energy Data Space	2
KPI12	Number of times that the data products were retrieved by users	0	≥ 1	2
KPI13	Energy services provided by exploiting a shared data product	0	≥ 1	2
KPI14	Personnel Upskilling: employees aware of data spaces and its usability	5	30	2
KPI15	Design and implementation of data sharing process to external stakeholders through data spaces	0	1 well-defined process handling quality and governance concerns	2

Table 11: Pilot 3 KPIs.

The first four KPIs concern collecting and preparing the necessary data for Pilot 3's objective and are an important aspect of the first iteration effort. As previously mentioned, the collected data originates from three sources:

- a. SCADA system measurements each containing three types of measurements (loads, voltages, and power) organised into CSV files,

- b. AMI measurements were obtained from HEDNO's Telemetry Center which are also organised into CSV files,
- c. One PowerFactory network model file that includes the physical topology and electrical parameters of the network.

More specifically, KPI1 refers to collecting 100% of the data required for performing simulations related to system planning, while KPI2 must be met in order to run the network simulation and optimisation tools efficiently since it sets a threshold for the minimum number of consumers or producers in a MV line in relation to the total apparent power installed.

KPI3 focuses on the physical aspects of the network, which are also necessary for system planning and involve uploading a PowerFactory network model file to the DATAMITE platform.

The data contained in the CSV files has also been stored in PostgreSQL databases, one for each dataset (SCADA and AMI) following the table structures mentioned previously. The PowerFactory file has been prepared and is available for the demonstration of Pilot 3 in test scenarios 1 and 2.

KPI4 ensures the inclusion of at least three different datasets in Pilot 3. These datasets contain all the data provided by HEDNO for Pilot 3, are sufficient for system planning simulations and are used in the first iteration of the demonstration, in scenarios 1 and 2. Apart from these three datasets (SCADA, AMI and PowerFactory), two more datasets are derived from the two PostgreSQL databases via connectors. By iteration 2, a sixth dataset will be integrated through the integration of S3 connector, linking DATAMITE with an S3-compatible storage service that contains the PowerFactory files.

KPIs 5, 6 and 7 refer to the successful integration of the DATAMITE components into the pilot. KPIs 5 and 6 focus on the internal process of setting up the necessary (virtual) infrastructure and systems for deployment and testing of the developed components and connectors necessary for the functionality of the pilot. Currently, an internal virtual machine was set up to host the initially developed DATAMITE components, which were deployed via a Docker swarm cluster. By the second iteration, all required components will be fully integrated into the pilot, thereby ensuring the validity of KPI7, which requires the deployment of more than three modules. Among the integrated components will be the *Data Sovereignty* and the *Access Control* components, which will be included respectively in test scenarios 4 and 3 – 7 in the second iteration.

KPI8 evaluates the processing of datasets by the *Data Governance*, *Data Quality*, or *Data Security* modules. At the current stage of implementation, the components included in the *security module have not yet been integrated into the infrastructure project pipelines*. However, various

components of the *Data Governance* module have been incorporated and are being utilised in test scenario 1 of the first iteration. Specifically, the *Data Governance Backend* and the *Metadata Repository* are used for storing metadata extracted from the datasets. By the second iteration, all modules and their respective components will be fully integrated.

The *Access Control* component will be used to manage access to the platform and to grant user permissions for various data-related functionalities. In test scenario 4, access and usage policies will be defined for data products, covering at least 80% of the available data used in the pilot, ensuring the validity of KPI9.

In the second iteration of the demonstration, the data-sharing capabilities of the DATAMITE framework will be utilised to perform a system planning simulation. The final four KPIs relate to the successful completion of the pilot, by facilitating a data exchange procedure between two partners and will be fully realised by the second iteration. Test scenario 6 refers to onboarding to a Gaia-X compliant data space, validating KPI10, while test scenario 7 will involve publishing a data product via an Energy Data Space, which validates KPI11. Subsequently, in test scenario 8, associated with KPI12, the objective is the downloading of a data product by a consumer through the Energy Data Space, concluding the demonstration.

System planning may be aided by either one of the following energy services provided by an energy service provider:

1. Sizing and siting of RES,
2. AI-based forecasting of (energy) generation and load,
3. Estimation of power state variables using AI-based state estimation algorithms.

The objective for validating KPI13 is the successful delivery of at least one of these energy services by the data consumer (partner CERTH) of the pilot back to the data provider (partner HEDNO).

Finally, the business value of the pilot is evaluated through KPI14 and KPI15, which pertain to improvements at the company level. Taking advantage of the training material prepared for DATAMITE, a 500% increase in personnel upskill is expected, allowing more researchers from within HEDNO to expand their knowledge of data spaces and actively utilise the tools of the framework to enhance their workflows. Moreover, KPI15 validates a streamlined process for data sharing through data spaces, which will expedite internal procedures regarding the preparation of data products (data gathering, quality assessment, policy definitions) and allow for more opportunities for monetisation and exploitation.

4.4. Pilot 4 - Leveraging Electricity Distribution Open Data

E-REDES, as an electricity Distribution System Operator (DSO), is one of the key energy stakeholders in the Portuguese energy matrix. Due to the nature of its activity, E-REDES plays the role of the metering data operator, which is responsible for collecting, validating, handling, and delivering metering data, based on consenting and security mechanisms. Furthermore, E-REDES deals with a significant amount of data from the High Voltage (HV), Medium Voltage (MV) and Low Voltage (LV) network operations. The most recent numbers show that E-REDES deals with more than 400 million data records every day, with a volume of 3 Terabytes (TB), which can be broken into the following categories:

- Daily time-of-use readings from smart meters (~3.6 M)
- Daily load curves from the smart meters in a 15-minute interval (~3.2 M)
- Daily events (5-10M)
 - Predictive network anomalies
 - Network modelling and load simulations
 - Outage management at LV level
 - Network registration
- Remote service orders executed (~0.9M)

E-REDES interacts with various stakeholders such as consumers, municipalities, the National Regulation Authority (NRA), energy suppliers, external service providers, and aggregators, amongst others, to manage and operate the electricity grid and to provide the necessary information mandated by the regulator. This means that data management and sharing play an important role in E-REDES activity as a DSO.

In addition, these stakeholders, together with other playing actors in the energy matrix such as universities, research entities, and energy communities, look to access their energy consumption and generation data, amongst other data from the network operation, to optimise their energy usage and generation profiles and to take part in new opportunities resulting from the energy transition such as flexibility provision to the electricity grids to enhance grid management while having incentives such as lower energy prices. E-REDES launched an Open Data Dedicated Platform in November 2022, which aims to share the network operation data aggregated by the company to society. With this platform, E-REDES keeps supporting transparency and digitalisation by making its data available to all. The company is evolving the open data solution

by leveraging and enriching datasets and combining them with new ones, notably to further create value for society and for the different stakeholders.

Due to an increased share of distributed generation and the electrification of different sectors, the number of devices connected to the energy system is growing. This is causing an increase in the number of data points and in the volume of data being collected and handled by the energy stakeholders, where DSOs such as E-REDES are included. Also, the energy system is becoming more integrated, with a cross-sector approach, which demands close collaboration between all the stakeholders involved in the system operation, where data management and sharing play an important role. The European Commission (EC) recognised in the Digitalisation of Energy System Action Plan (DESAP) the importance of data sharing on the new energy matrix and stated that it is necessary to have a dedicated infrastructure to enhance data sharing between the energy stakeholders. This will be achieved through the development of a Common European Energy Data Space (CEEDS).

E-REDES is leading the pilot 4 implementation, which foresees leverage of its open data portal and testing data sharing to external stakeholders through the Common European Energy Data Spaces (CEEDS). The DATAMITE Framework is expected to ensure proper access and dissemination to the open data products through the energy data spaces, which is expected to create a common data sharing channel mechanism, enrich the spectrum of users of the datasets and enhance their value to society. In addition, the economic impact of the investment in connecting to a data space will be evaluated from an investment and maintenance perspective and from a communication viewpoint. The high-level architecture of the pilot can be seen in Figure 29: High-level architecture of Pilot 4

Figure 29: High-level architecture of Pilot 4

4.4.1. Test Scenarios

The E-REDES pilot implementation will be demonstrated and validated in three levels.

4.4.1.1. Level 1 – Data Collection, Handle and Validation, and Sharing at E-REDES

This level is related to the data collection, handling and validation carried out by the E-REDES BI Application (BI4D) and is composed of the lower 3 layers represented in Figure 29. The same processes developed to build the datasets made available at the E-REDES Open Data portal are being used to build and share the datasets and the data artefacts from Table 13 needed in the context of the DATAMITE project. These processes, as previously mentioned, can be divided into three main steps: data collection, data aggregation and validation, and data sharing.

The first step, *data collection*, refers to the part of the process where raw data is gathered from replicas of the operational systems or from the E-REDES DATAHUB, if the necessary data is already available. The DATAHUB provides consolidated and aggregated data from various sources across commercial, asset, network, and energy domains. The replicated data is asynchronous with the operational systems, being updated with the necessary frequency with batch (less frequent) or micro-batch (more frequent) processes. Whenever possible, data from the E-REDES DATAHUB is used, as it is already normalised at the Entity level and aggregated

at the data mart level, making it easier and more efficient to work with. Regarding data access, since data is stored in Azure storage accounts (ADLS Gen 2) in the form of structured data (avro, parquet or delta), legacy connectors to External Storage Locations (mount points) are used to establish a connection between the Databricks environment and necessary information. In some cases, additional reference data is needed to complement the specified output. This data is stored on the BI4D storage account and is accessed via the previously described method.

The second step, *data aggregation and validation*, refers to the necessary operations that ensure that data is handled according to the specified business rules and the output is coherent with the information shared on other occasions: regulatory reports and targeted sharing to other stakeholders (e.g.: municipalities). This step is divided into three main activities: data wrangling, pipeline orchestration and data sharing. In the data wrangling activity, all the aggregation operations are done using Databricks, enabling the implementation of pipelines using the Spark engine, needed to work with large volumes of data, such as metering data and its association with client master data. This step is also where data validation takes place to ensure that the output does not contain any sensitive information and is aggregated at the level it needs to be. Pipeline orchestration is done using Azure Data Factory (ADF), where data wrangling processes are linked in the necessary order and executed according to the defined triggers for each dataset.

The third and final step, data sharing, is where the final aggregated datasets are copied from the BI4D storage account to an SFTP service used to ingest the data into the E-REDES Open Data application. In addition, a step to copy the datasets selected to be shared on the DATAMITE project to the project's unmanaged storage account has been implemented.

On this level, regarding pilot 4, what has to be validated is the provision of the open datasets and data artefacts from the BI4D storage to the dedicated ADLS Gen 2 for the project. This level was deployed and tested in the first iteration phase, which was supposed to be completed by February 2025 (M26).

4.4.1.2. Level 2 – DATAMITE Framework: Preparation for Data Sharing

This level is composed of all the necessary activities to prepare the datasets and data artefacts to create a data product for data sharing. It will start with the ingestion and storage of the datasets using the *Data Ingestion* and *Storage* tools from the *Data Support Tools module*. The metadata will be extracted through the *Data Discovery Connector* and passed on to the *Data Governance Backend*, which will store it in the *Metadata Repository*. Then, E-REDES, as a data provider defines the quality rules, which are evaluated using the tools from the *Data Quality Module*. This

task ensures that the data artefacts and the datasets that will constitute the data products have enough quality and allows the data provider to deploy the necessary tools if the quality results are not satisfactory. Complementing the quality rules, there is a set of KPIs listed in the *KPI Library* that will be evaluated. The quality evaluation results, including quality rules and KPIs, will be forwarded to the *Data Governance Backend*, which will store the evaluation in the *Metadata Repository*.

All the information related to the dataset, the data artefacts, and the evaluations will be available to be consulted on the dictionary, catalogue and glossary on the front end, and the data versions will be maintained and stored.

On this level, the definition and testing of the quality rules to be defined by E-REDES, together with the retrieval and storage of the metadata corresponding to the datasets, and the proper access to the terms on the *dictionary*, *catalogue* and *glossary* at the frontend.

This level started to be deployed and tested in the first iteration phase and will be completed by September 2025 (M33).

4.4.1.3. Level 3 – DATAMITE Framework: Data Sharing

This level is related to data sharing through the open data portal and the energy data spaces. E-REDES will create different types of data products, using the data product composition together with the harmonisation component from the support tools module. The metadata will be provided to the data spaces and the portal using the *EDC connector*. It needs to be ensured that E-REDES is enlisted and onboarded in the data spaces and that complies with all of the IDS and Gaia-X requirements.

The data consumer will be able to access the information of the data products provided by E-REDES and will be able to retrieve the products using the *EDC connector*.

On this level, what needs to be validated is the onboarding of E-REDES on the data spaces, the provision of the metadata from the datasets to the open data portal and the data spaces, the access by the consumer to this metadata on the portal and the data spaces, the composition of the data products and their provision using the connectors. This level will be deployed and tested in the second iteration phase, which is supposed to be completed by September 2025 (M33).

Test Scenarios

Figure 30: Pilot 4 test scenarios

The three levels are divided into two scenarios, which can be observed in Figure 30. In the first scenario, which corresponds to Level 1, the open datasets are validated by E-REDES. If the validation is approved, the process proceeds to Level 2 where the dataset will be uploaded to the dedicated database for the project MS Azure sandbox. Otherwise, the process is interrupted. Level 1 involves only an internal demonstration as it occurs within E-REDES internal systems.

In the following step of scenario 1, which corresponds to Level 2, the dataset or data artefact will be ingested in DATAMITE through the *Data Ingestion and Storage* components. This process will deploy the *Discovery Connector* component to store the metadata in the Metadata Repository and request a profiling of the data. A set of KPIs will be evaluated through the *Quality Evaluator*

and store the results in the *Metadata Repository*. The set of KPIs is composed of default rules in the *KPI Library* and rules defined by E-REDES (data provider). Lastly, the datasets will be published. The publication of the dataset serves as an external demonstration and validation.

In scenario 2, which corresponds to Level 3, the data consumer accesses the information related to the data product on the open data portal or on the energy data space, ensuring that E-REDES is registered as a data provider in the data space. The data products are defined by the data producer, in this case, E-REDES, using the *Data Product Composition* component, and then are published in the open data portal and the CEEDS for consumption. The access control and the sovereignty tools will assess the data products available to the consumer for placing a data request. The data request enters the open data portal or the CEEDS, where the information related to the data products defined by E-REDES is made available through the *EDC Connector*. The *Data Product Composition* component will then retrieve the data and harmonised metadata, aggregate it, and share the final data product. The attainment of the final data product serves as an external demonstration and validation.

4.4.2. Solution implementation

The Pilot 4 is implemented in a Microsoft (MS) Azure environment to align with the company's existing infrastructure. This approach leverages the developers' knowledge of Azure services, minimising the time required to learn new tools and integrate them into the current infrastructure.

The Azure environment includes the following resources:

- Virtual Machine (VM): hosts the DATAMITE components running in containerised instances using Docker
- Storage Account: serves as a storage solution for the datasets
- Databricks service: connected to both the Storage Account and the VM, allowing access to the datasets, making changes to them, and connecting to the DATAMITE components

The Databricks service will be used first to integrate the pilot functionalities. Given its connection to the Storage Account, it can access and modify the datasets as needed. Additionally, the Databricks service is connected to the VM, enabling API calls to the DATAMITE components. Secondly, adding a Data Factory to the Azure environment is being considered. This addition will enable the deployment of necessary Databricks services upon a request from a Data user.

Figure 31: Implementation in Azure

Figure 31 is a representation of the resources used in Azure for the pilot implementation. The three main resources listed previously (VM, Storage Account, and Databricks) are delimited by red rectangles. The Azure Cosmos DB (top row, third from left to right) is a NoSQL database resource designed for compatibility with MongoDB, which is a requirement for the component *User Defined Rules Generator*. The remaining resources are automatically created to allocate cloud memory and ensure network connection among the main resources.

Pilot 4 is planned to have the following architecture:

Figure 32: Pilot 4's architecture

The architecture starts within E-REDES internal systems, where all the processes detailed in [Level 1](#) are executed. Given these processes are internal, they do not rely on any components of the DATAMITE's framework.

The datasets to be shared with the DATAMITE framework are built and aggregated on the E-REDES internal systems and are ingested directly into the framework using a mount point to the Azure storage account (ADLS Gen 2). This Azure resource is included in the infrastructure and stores the datasets after ingestion. The previous two processes form the *Data Ingestion and Storage Mechanism*.

The storage of a new dataset triggers the *Data Discovery Connectors*, more specifically the Azure connector due to E-REDES infrastructure, to retrieve the dataset's metadata. This metadata is stored in the *Metadata Repository*, using the *Data Governance Backend* as an intermediary.

In addition, the storage of a new dataset also prompts the *Quality Evaluator* to perform a profiling of the dataset. This profiling includes rules inputted by users, which can be seen in Table 12, which are added using the *User Defined Rules Generator*, and a set of default KPIs defined in the *KPI Library*. The results of the data profiling are sent to the *Data Governance Backend* for storage in the *Metadata Repository*.

Rule Name	DQ Dimension	KPI
Parish Total Installed Power Accuracy Validation	Accuracy	(# of registers with potencia_instalada_total < 0) < 5%
Parish Total Number of Luminaires Accuracy Validation	Accuracy	(# of registers with luminarias < 0) < 5%
Special Public Lighting Lamp Type Completeness Validation: Is null	Completeness	(tipo_lampada = null) < 20%
Special Public Lighting Lamp Accuracy Power Validation: Less than or equal to 0	Accuracy	(potencia_lampada <= 0) < 20%
Special Public Lighting Lamp Completeness Power Validation: Is Null	Completeness	(potencia_lampada = null) < 20%
Special Public Lighting Lamp Type Validity Validation: Is in [LED, Iodeto Metálico, Fluorescente, Indução, Mercúrio, Sódio]	Validity	(tipo_lampada is in [LED, Iodeto Metálico, Fluorescente, Indução, Mercúrio, Sódio]) > 80%
Special Public Lighting Height Completeness Validation: Is Null	Completeness	(altura = null) < 20%
Public Lighting Columns Lamp Type Completeness Validation: Is null	Completeness	(tipo_lampada = null) < 20%
Public Lighting Columns Lamp Accuracy Power Validation: Less than or equal to 0	Accuracy	(potencia_lampada <= 0) < 20%
Public Lighting Columns Lamp Completeness Power Validation: Is Null	Completeness	(potencia_lampada = null) < 20%

Rule Name	DQ Dimension	KPI
Public Lighting Columns Lamp Type Validity Validation: Is in [LED, Iodeto Metálico, Fluorescente, Indução, Mercúrio, Sódio]	Validity	(tipo_lampada is in [LED, Iodeto Metálico, Fluorescente, Indução, Mercúrio, Sódio]) > 80%
Public Lighting Columns Height Completeness Validation: Is Null	Completeness	(altura = null) < 20%
Public Lighting Arms Lamp Type Completeness Validation: Is null	Completeness	(tipo_lampada = null) < 20%
Public Lighting Arms Lamp Accuracy Power Validation: Less than or equal to 0	Accuracy	(potencia_lampada <= 0) < 20%
Public Lighting Arms Lamp Completeness Power Validation: Is Null	Completeness	(potencia_lampada = null) < 20%
Public Lighting Arms Lamp Type Validity Validation: Is in [LED, Iodeto Metálico, Fluorescente, Indução, Mercúrio, Sódio]	Validity	(tipo_lampada is in [LED, Iodeto Metálico, Fluorescente, Indução, Mercúrio, Sódio]) > 80%
Public Lighting Arms Height Completeness Validation: Is Null	Completeness	(altura = null) < 20%

Table 12: Quality rules defined for Pilot 4

Once metadata extraction and dataset profiling are complete, the dataset is ready to be published in the *DATAMITE frontend*.

On the other end of the pilot's architecture are the CEEDS and the open data portal, connecting to the framework through the *EDC Connector*. The connector transmits to the framework the data requests from the data space. The request is dispatched to the *Data Product Composition* component, which extracts and compiles the required information. This component accesses the *Data Storage* to read the datasets required for the request. It also extracts the metadata associated with the datasets from the *Metadata Repository* using the *Data Governance Backend* as an intermediary. This metadata is then standardised by the *Data Harmonisation*. Once the data

and metadata are aggregated, the data product is shared through the *EDC Connector* into the data space where the request originated.

To ensure the correct flow in the framework, several critical components are also included, though not previously mentioned.

Within the *Data Governance Module*, there are two additional components. One is *Data Versioning*, which aims to store the original data and subsequent additions as deltas (incremental changes). Given that the framework uses Databricks to establish connections among the components, Delta Lake for Spark will be used to track the multiple versions of the same data. The other component is *Data Lineage*, which intends to track and visualize the flow of data. This functionality is ensured through Databricks Unity Catalogue.

Lastly, the framework includes a *Data Security Module* formed by two components: *Data Sovereignty* and *Access Control*. *Data Sovereignty* establishes data usage policies between E-REDES (data provider) and data consumers, enforced during data exchange within data spaces. *Access Control* implements mechanisms for fine-grained user access and permissions, determining the data assets available to each data consumer based on their access level.

One of the approaches to integrate and test the components from level 2 was through the deployment of the prototype made available in the Aachen Plenary Meeting. The DATAMITE technical team created a prototype to demonstrate the integration of the framework components. The team provided a tutorial to test the prototype in the pilot's infrastructure. Some files in the prototype needed modification for the prototype to function correctly. The goal was to demonstrate the components integration, including the frontend, by uploading in bulk a dataset example to the prototype. This upload would trigger the metadata extraction as well as the data profiling, which would be available in the frontend. Additionally, the prototype stores the uploaded datasets as data artefacts, maintaining a versioning of the same dataset, which demonstrates the *Data Versioning* component.

Datasets

The pilot will be tested by using 7 datasets and 6 data artefacts that can be seen in the Table 13. The datasets are open datasets that are available on the open data portal and the data artefacts are the raw data used to compose the public lighting and telecommunications open datasets. The data artefacts will be used to be able to compose different data products from the ones available on the open data portal. The Databricks service ensures the connection to both the Storage

Account and the VM, allowing users to access the datasets, make changes to them, and connect to the DATAMITE components.

Name	Description	Size
Connection to Power Generation Centres	The dataset contains information about the number of executed grid connection requests and connection power for new renewable production units per municipality. Includes production units of self-consumption (PUSC) with power greater than 1MW	64 kb
Network Connections	The dataset contains information about the number completed grid connection requests by municipalities	55 kb
Substation Capacity	The dataset contains information about the type, position and power capacity of the E-REDES primary substations	132 kb
Connections to Renewables	The dataset contains information about the number of new grid connections associated with renewable energy generation	3 kb
Connections Associated with EVs	The dataset contains information about the number of new grid connections associated with electric mobility per municipality	12 kb
Telco Infrastructures	The dataset contains information of the low voltage poles that are able to support telco cables	3.4 GB
Telco Infrastructures (Poles Artefact)	The data artefact contains the raw data used to calculate the results shared on Telco Infrastructures dataset referring to the Low Voltage Poles	2 GB
Telco Infrastructures (Lines Artefact)	The data artefact contains the raw data used to calculate the results shared on Telco Infrastructures dataset referring to the Low Voltage line segments	3 GB
Public Lighting Luminaries	The dataset contains information about the characterisation of public lighting by district, county and parish	912 kb

Name	Description	Size
Public Lighting Luminaries (Arms Artefact)	The data artefact contains the raw data used to calculate the results shared on Public Lighting Luminaries dataset referring to the Public Lighting Arms	360 MB
Public Lighting Luminaries (Columns Artefact)	The data artefact contains the raw data used to calculate the results shared on Public Lighting Luminaries dataset referring to the Public Lighting Columns	300 MB
Public Lighting Luminaries (Specialised Artefact)	The data artefact contains the raw data used to calculate the results shared on Public Lighting Luminaries dataset referring to the Specialised Public Lighting	7 MB

Table 13: Pilot 4 datasets and data artefacts

4.4.3. Training Materials planned

As mentioned in the previous section, the pilot will be tested and validated in 3 levels, divided into two scenarios. Firstly, after the framework is integrated in both phases, the DATAMITE framework will be made available to the E-REDES team responsible for the open data delivery process and to the BI4D team to test all the module functionalities that were integrated to validate the expected results in each phase, and to get feedback on design and implementation. To facilitate the testing, a demonstration video will be developed, and a demonstration session will be scheduled to present the functionalities and explain how to use the framework.

After the testing and validation from both teams of the 2nd scenario, the DATAMITE framework tool will be made available to other relevant departments in E-REDES in order to test the data sharing through the open data portal and through the energy data spaces and to explore new use cases for the utilisation of the DATAMITE framework, to complement the already foreseen use cases that were suggested in the 1st E-REDES Business Exploitation Workshop that occurred in September 2024. During the 2nd iteration phase, the tools developed in WP4, such as the data maturity module, will also be made available to be tested and to complement the results from the technical demonstration.

4.4.4. Test Campaign

As mentioned in the section related to the test scenarios, the pilot will be deployed and tested in 3 levels, as it can be seen in Figure 30, and it will be divided into two iteration phases, which are

described in Table 14 and Table 15. The 1st phase is composed of level one and level two and the deadline is set until the end of February 2025 (M26). In this phase, level one was already tested and validated, and it was planned that E-REDES would start the deployment of level two, which is currently being done. In the 2nd iteration phase, which is planned to be completed by September 2025 (M35), levels two and three will be deployed, tested and validated. The iteration phases were established according to the demonstration plan foreseen in the DATAMITE grant agreement and to accommodate the different development phases of the DATAMITE framework, which were defined between the technical partners and the pilots.

Iteration Phase 1	
Description	The first iteration focuses on preparing the Azure infrastructure to deploy the DATAMITE components and access the datasets and data artefacts to be used in the project by creating and deploying the resources. It will also be composed by the initial deployment of the <i>data quality</i> and <i>data governance module</i> components and the definition of the quality rules. In this phase, it is expected that the infrastructure is ready to be used for the deployment, that a discovery connector is created to ensure access to the datasets and artefacts, and that the bundled components from the first development phase of the project can be deployed.
Scenarios	Test Scenario 1
Timeline	M21-M26

Table 14: First iteration for Pilot 4

Iteration Phase 2	
Description	The second phase will start with the testing and validation of the deployment of the quality and governance mechanisms. Then, data products will be defined from the datasets and artefacts, and all of the components related to the security and sharing modules will be deployed, tested and validated. In this phase, it is expected that E-REDES can evaluate the quality of the datasets using the rules defined in the first phase, that all of the <i>data governance components</i> are functioning properly, that data products can be defined, using the <i>data products composition</i> tool, and that metadata can be provided and that data can be shared through an Energy Data Space.

Iteration Phase 2	
Scenarios	Test Scenarios 1-2
Timeline	M27-M35

Table 15: Second iteration for Pilot 4

4.4.5. Feedback for improving design

For iteration phase 1, we have gathered feedback on the implementation of various components. The *Data Discovery Connectors* component was implemented by cloning the code from the repository into the pilot's infrastructure. The solution is Dockerised, so a container was created to run the component. However, an issue arose when attempting to follow the repository instructions to make an API call and retrieve metadata from datasets: a connector for Azure storage account had not been developed. This made it impossible to establish a connection and extract metadata. To address this, E-REDES developed an Azure connector by following examples from other available connectors. This Azure connector was tested internally and worked correctly, returning metadata from the datasets in the Azure storage account. The Azure connector has been shared with the DATAMITE technical team for validation.

The implementation of the *Quality Evaluator* in the pilot is currently on standby. Although E-REDES cloned the code from the repository and created a container for this component, starting the container and making the API calls as indicated resulted in an internal error. Upon investigation, the technical team found that the component was unable to run standalone. The component was designed to work by calling the API and supplying the columns to evaluate, but it requires a prepared payload given the pipeline created by the team. The technical team is currently working on resolving this issue.

Regarding the *Data Governance Backend*, E-REDES cloned the repository code and created the container. The primary problem is the lack of information about API endpoints in the repository for this component, which prevents E-REDES from connecting the multiple components that require the *Data Governance Backend*, making the whole *Data Governance module* still fully integrated and validated.

The Metadata Repository is also in an early stage of development since there is still missing information on steps to implement the component in the infrastructure.

The *front end* is key to users' interaction with the infrastructure. The code in the respective repository was cloned to the pilot's infrastructure, and a container was created, similar to some of the previous components. The port used by the *front end* was made available, allowing access via the provided address. Nonetheless, to the establishment of a connection between the frontend and the components is still to be developed, integrated and tested. As of this moment, the frontend integrated into the pilot 4 works segregated from the other components, having only simulated or empty values.

Lastly, the prototype still exhibits some integration issues between the components. The *Data Storage component*, which uses MinIO, was not correctly storing the uploaded datasets. Checking the frontend, it only stored some metadata but not the data values. This integration issue prevented the *Quality Evaluator* of performing the data profiling and presenting the KPIs.

4.4.6. Validation KPIs

The KPIs and internal KPIs defined for pilot 4 can be observed in Table 16 and Table 17. The final KPIs will only be calculated after the end of the 2nd iteration phase since they are related to the data product data sharing. Within the start of the 1st iteration phase, it was possible to achieve the targeted KPI 1 since with the infrastructure developed to access and deploy the datasets and artefacts in the MS Azure environment was able to complete the 1st level of the 1st scenario, since the datasets and artefacts can be accessed in the framework. The other internal KPIs will only be calculated in the next phases of the pilot deployment.

KPI	Description	Baseline	Target
KPI1	Number of national and international users accessing open data	~3000	Increase [10% to 30%]
KPI2	Number of integrated datasets in the DATAMITE framework	0	12
KPI3	Number of data products created and shared through Data Spaces	0	> 6
KPI4	Average cost of exploiting and delivering open data	EUR 170 000/year	< 20%

Table 16: Pilot 4 tentative KPIs

Internal KPI	Description	Baseline	Target	Current
I1	Number of the selected datasets and artefacts shared in the pilot sandbox	0	12	12
I2	Number of data products ready to be provided to the data space	0	≥ 5	0
I3	Number of data products created	0	≥ 1	0
I4	Number of developed connectors compatible with the internal system to be deployed	0	≥ 1	1
I5	Number of the metadata of the dataset shared in the identified data spaces	0	≥ 5	0
I6	Number of times that users retrieved the data products	0	≥ 1	0

Table 17: Pilot 4 internal KPIs

4.5. Pilot 5 - Connecting eDWIN to Data Markets

A vast quantity of data is produced and processed by digital agricultural systems. This data is often, however, difficult to be reused by other systems due to proprietary data structures or access protocols. Even some of the governmental data sets, which should be following the open data approach, are not easily accessible or in an interoperable manner. Moreover, integrating only the data and services from public institutions is limiting the overall scope of offer for farmers as many of the services are provided by the commercial sector, both SMEs and larger industrial partners. The main goal of this pilot is to facilitate the sharing of agricultural data and provide monetisation possibilities for data in agriculture ecosystems in Poland.

The eDWIN project (<https://www.edwin.gov.pl/>) is a national project in Poland that provides tools for farm management, weather and forecast data, pest monitoring, AI-powered decision support models, and communication between farmers and advisors. With 20,000 farms nowadays and over 180,000 fields, eDWIN aims to support up to 200,000 users, mostly farmers and advisors. Besides the data provided by the farmers, a network of meteorological ground stations provides agri-meteo data and statistical information (operated by 16 Regional Agriculture Advisory Centres), a Farm Management System - Virtual Farm application, and ground observations of the

occurrence of diseases and pests. At the current state of the eDWIN project, enabling secure data sharing and the possibility of data monetisation of collected and processed data is of high priority. Agrego (<https://agrego.pl/>) is another system that could benefit by building on top of agrifood sharing data space. Agrego is a platform that helps manage farms and production within producer groups. It allows for accurate record-keeping and data analysis and is partially integrated with ARiMR (Polish National Agricultural Agency) systems for easier access to agricultural production data. Agrego also participates in the process of documenting food quality and passporting of agricultural products, increasing consumer confidence in Polish food.

Figure 33: Pilot 5 high-level architecture.

Figure 33 represents the pilot's high-level architecture. Starting from the bottom, we have a list of data sources, including eDWIN and Agrego, as well as other possible providers. Datasets are

then harmonised and shared with the DATAMITE platform layer. The final step is publishing the data products further to data space frameworks such as Gaia-X or Pontus-X.

4.5.1. Test Scenarios

At the beginning of the project, three main objectives for Pilot 5 were chosen. A short summary is presented below:

- **Data catalogue** – use the mechanisms of the DATAMITE to create the Data Catalogue for open data, dictionaries, common standards, and common ontologies for agrifood data. This objective is the basis for implementing the other two objectives. We assume that chosen models, metadata, and their structures prepared and integrated on the eDWIN platform will be published on the DATAMITE platform. Mechanisms prepared in this way should be promoted for wider use in companies and institutions. The objective assumes the use of components of the DATAMITE platform to create data products.
- **Polish Agricultural Data Space** – this objective is focused on creating a Polish Agricultural Data Space – a data space and a marketplace for entities to publish data products. It will be used to share chosen data sets coming from the eDWIN ecosystem as well as Agrego production data. Polish Agricultural Data Space can be seen as a very important mechanism for the collaboration between stakeholders. This objective assumes two mechanisms: open and free data sharing, as well as data tracing. The second is data trading in monetisation mechanisms. Publishing on the Polish Agricultural Data Space should be possible by utilising DATAMITE mechanisms, including data broker integration.
- **Data sharing** – using the DATAMITE mechanisms and components to share data between sets of companies for common business-oriented goals. This goal can be achieved in two stages: data quality preparation and data sharing. In this scenario, we will focus on the user's use of data in various systems and applications. The primary end-user problem is reusing data instead of rewriting or copying it.

To achieve these goals, integration of 3 test levels is planned for the pilot. Also, for each test level, we specify more detailed test scenarios that will help validate and demonstrate the pilot's integration with the DATAMITE project:

Level 1 – Data preparation, normalisation of the data sources, ingestion of the data

The first level covers the topic of data sets that will be involved in the Pilot. The most significant source of data is the eDWIN project, which collects and processes a plethora of data involving

farmers, their fields, types of crops, plant protection products used, as well as more general information like weather and forecast data from surrounding area or dictionary-style data such as a list of plant protection products or disease and pests' dictionary. Likewise, other platforms collect similar data from farmers, like platform Agrego from IDFS, which is also involved in the pilot and collects production data from fields.

After careful business and use case assessments by data owners, a subset of the data to be shared was chosen. Those datasets could prove to be valuable to other systems and researchers and improve the offerings of services by being correlated with new, high-quality data sets. The next step is ensuring that the chosen data is in a normalised form. For each dataset, a data pipeline will be created and deployed, following the steps of obtaining the data, cleaning the data, and normalising the data.

The specific test scenarios for Level 1 are described below.

4.5.1.1. Scenario 1 - Automatic collection of data sets from related systems

This test scenario involves the preparation and/or configuration of specific API endpoints, Database ports, and other connection means to obtain the chosen data sets. It also involves preparing a set of services that will contact those endpoints to obtain datasets for the preparation of further operations on the data sets.

4.5.1.2. Scenario 2 - Creation and deployment of data pipelines

DATAMITE components used: Data Support Tools (Data Harmonisation)

Data sets involved within the pilot must be in a specific format. This means that the data set must be already returned from the system in proper format and schema or that a specific data pipeline will be created that involves, e.g. data clean-up, normalisation and usage of agrifood domain models.

Level 2 – Deployment of DATAMITE platform and DATAMITE components, deployment of Polish Agricultural Data Space

At this level, technical work to deploy the DATAMITE platform and its components will be performed. The first step will be the preparation of a specific infrastructure fulfilling the technical requirements of the platform. When the platform is available, it will be deployed on the pilot infrastructure and will be kept operational - this involves installing any updates, patches or additional components that will appear during the project.

One of the goals of Pilot 5 is to create a data space and marketplace for the agrifood domain in Poland. On this test level, an analysis and review of possible data spaces will be performed to determine the best fit for the requirements. The data space and the necessary data broker(s) will then be deployed and configured.

Specific test cases for Level 2:

4.5.1.3. Scenario 3 - Configuration of infrastructure and deployment of DATAMITE platform and necessary components

DATAMITE components used: DATAMITE platform, Data Discovery Tools, Data Governance Module (Data Catalogue, Data Dictionary, Data Glossary), Data Sharing Module (IDSA & Gaia-X connectors & components)

This test scenario covers a successful deployment and configuration of the DATAMITE platform on PSNC premises. This includes a successful onboarding process with the usage of available tools from "IDSA & Gaia-X connectors & components". Basic functionalities of the DATAMITE platform will be tested in this scenario, such as uploading data sets into the platform and creating glossaries, terms, and schemas.

4.5.1.4. Scenario 4 - Deployment of data space/marketplace for agrifood domain in Poland

DATAMITE components used: Data Sharing Module (IDSA & Gaia-X connectors & components)

This scenario will cover the deployment and configuration of the chosen data space platform. Direct publishing of the data sets on the data space will be performed during this scenario.

Level 3 – Sharing the data products on the DATAMITE Platform and Polish Agricultural Data Space

The final level of integration between the pilot and DATAMITE covers the creation, sharing and publishing of the data products. DATAMITE platform will be utilised with any necessary additional components, from which Data Quality (Quality Evaluator, KPI Library) is of special importance for this pilot, as the quality of data is very important for correct decisions during food production.

Specific test cases for Level 3:

4.5.1.5. Scenario 5 - Publishing data sets on DATAMITE portal

DATAMITE components used: DATAMITE portal, Data Discovery Module, Data Sharing Module (Data Product Composition)

From the pilot's data sets, data products will be created within the DATAMITE portal, utilising available Data Sharing Module tools.

4.5.1.6. Scenario 6 - Use the DATAMITE platform to publish data products on the Polish Agricultural Data Space

DATAMITE components used: DATAMITE portal, Data Sharing Module (Data Product Composition, Brokers & plugins for other targets [Pontus-X]),

The data products created in test scenario 5 will be published on different target platforms like Gaia-X and Polish Agricultural Data Space hosted by PSNC. This scenario requires a working broker & plugin for Pontus-X.

4.5.1.7. Scenario 7 – Enhancing data products with Data Quality Module

DATAMITE components used: DATAMITE portal, Data Sharing Module (Data Product Composition), Data Quality Module (User Defined Rules Generator, KPI Library, Quality Evaluator)

Pilot's data products will be enhanced by using components from, e.g., the Data Quality module of DATAMITE.

4.5.2. Solution implementation

The Pilot 5 revolves around existing systems and applications. The main one is the eDWIN project. It provides a set of APIs, as well as a set of user applications, enabling different actors to exchange data. The APIs, available as OpenAPI specifications via Swagger, provide access to the core functionalities, including access to the data. eDWIN provides different mobile and Web applications for farmers, advisors and other stakeholders. Internally, Apache Kafka is used for data transfer and storage of events as well as separate raw data registries (including a time series DB, SQL and document databases) and registries designed to index the data producers like sensors, data points or references.

eDWIN includes an Identity and Access Management (IAM) System, implements an identity tool with OAuth 2.0 standard and on top that uses OpenID Connect (OIDC) protocol that provides authentication and includes features for obtaining user consent during the authentication process.

OIDC facilitates Single Sign-On, allowing users to log in once and access multiple applications or services without needing to re-authenticate separately for each. In the eDWIN platform, SSO stands as the primary tool for consent and permission management.

eDWIN uses OpenID (Keycloak) to integrate with various Identity Providers, including the Polish national login.gov.pl. Data sharing APIs have restricted access, controlled by access policies, written in access tokens distributed by Keycloak, which implements OAuth 2.0 standards.

The other system that is interested in sharing the data through Pilot 5 is Agrego. It provides a platform for farmers, agricultural producer groups, and advisors. Built on ASP.NET MVC, Agrego focuses on delivering essential functionalities to its users through a well-structured internal communication system.

Agrego utilises ASP.NET Identity 2.0 for user authentication, providing a robust framework for managing user identities. In addition to this, Agrego includes a custom, manageable system for roles and permissions. This system is designed to grant data access to authorised users based on their roles within the platform.

The production data within Agrego is stored on an MS SQL server. The database schema is designed to handle standard relational data, ensuring efficient storage and retrieval of agricultural production records. This setup supports the complex data requirements of farmers, producer groups, and advisors by maintaining data integrity and providing reliable access.

Agrego provides a cohesive platform where farmers, producer groups, and advisors can collaborate and share information. The user interface is designed to be intuitive, facilitating easy data entry and retrieval. The platform supports a range of agricultural activities, from production tracking to advisory services, enhancing productivity and decision-making.

Both platforms, eDWIN and Agrego, are essential for Pilot 5 functioning, as they provide the data sets that are planned to be transformed and shared via the DATAMITE platform.

Standards and metadata

In order to foster (semantic) interoperability across different systems/tools, enabling them to exchange data unambiguously and to provide an integrated view over heterogeneous datasets, DATAMITE use cases will use standard and well-known vocabularies as a common language to represent the data. Regarding the agriculture use case, we will adopt and apply the Agriculture Information Model (AIM). AIM has been designed following a layered and modular approach, and it is realised as a suite of ontologies implemented in line with best practices, reusing existing

standards and well-scoped dominant models as much as possible and establishing alignments between them to enable their interoperability and the integration of existing data. AIM is scalable and can be easily extended to address additional needs and incorporate new concepts, maintaining its consistency and compliance.

Datasets in Pilot 5

Table 18 below represents all datasets that were planned to be integrated and shared within DATAMITE.

Datasets	Description	Variety	Volume & Velocity	Availability
eDWIN agri-meteo (WODR, PSNC)	600 agri-meteo stations. Measurements located in rural areas.	~10 variables: location, owner, name, code, temperatures, humidity, rainfall, wind speed and direction, air pressure...	1-hour frequency samples, >1 GB / year	Public / extendable with private and commercial data
eDWIN pests (WODR, PSNC/ Institute of Plant Protection)	Knowledge database	~15 variables, covering names, descriptions, links, growing conditions, pests	~1 GB, generally static	Public
eDWIN market data products for agricultural production (WODR, PSNC)	prices of fertilizers and plant protection products	~15 variables, covering names, dates, prices, sources	~10 MB per day important time variability and history	Public, limited access

Datasets	Description	Variety	Volume & Velocity	Availability
Demeter AIM (Demeter platform)	EU Agriculture Inform. Model for interoperable platforms	~100 parameters and model descriptions	<1MB, static	Public
EDWIN agricultural dictionaries (WODR, PSNC)	EDWIN platform – polish public national agriculture advisory Integrated dictionaries	~20-30 variables, covering id's, codes, names, links, translations	<1 MB, slowly shifting, most early	Public
Agrego production data	Agricultural production data incl. avg. production, production resources usage etc.	2-3 datasets ~ 15 variables incl. names, amounts, locations	~10MB per year, increasing, current and historical	Private, anonymized

Table 18: Pilot 5 initial datasets selection description

eDWIN weather data

In the eDWIN platform, weather data from around 600 weather stations (currently) is collected. The data comes from different systems, platforms and owners, but during the ingestion process the data is normalized and stored in eDWIN time-series database. The data is then shared via REST API within the platform for internal use by different services as well as publicly open, however, with limited functionality. One set of APIs exposes the weather data in AIM model. Figure 34 presents a single weather record in JSON-LD schema.

There are two main dataset types regarding weather data that Pilot 5 has an interest in sharing within the data spaces. First is data from each individual weather station, collected in a specific

timeframe. This includes both raw readings as well as aggregations over a period of time, e.g. daily aggregations from a single station like maximum/average/minimum temperature, humidity etc.

The second weather dataset is already processed data from a specific region. The territory of Poland is divided into voivodeships (provinces); these are further divided into powiats (counties or districts), and these, in turn, are divided into gminas (communes or municipalities). For each of those administrative division levels aggregated and processed data will be shared.

This dataset is already in an AIM-compliant model and does not require additional usage of DATAMITE framework components at this stage of integration to normalize its model.

Pending approval by the European Commission

```
{
  "@type": "http://www.w3.org/ns/sosa/Observation",
  "@context": {
    "aim": "https://w3id.org/demeter/agri-context.jsonld",
    "precipitationRaw2": "https://smartdatamodels.org/dataModel.Weather/precipitation",
    "precipitationRaw1": "https://smartdatamodels.org/dataModel.Weather/precipitation",
    "airPressure": "http://foodie-cloud.com/model/foodie#pressure",
    "soilTemp0_05": "https://smartdatamodels.org/dataModel.Agrifood/soilTemperature",
    "soilTempDepth0_2": "https://smartdatamodels.org/dataModel.Agrifood/soilTemperature",
    "soilTempDepth0_1": "https://smartdatamodels.org/dataModel.Agrifood/soilTemperature",
    "soilTempDepth1_0": "https://smartdatamodels.org/dataModel.Agrifood/soilTemperature",
    "measurementDate": "https://smartdatamodels.org/dateObserved",
    "soilTempDepth0_5": "https://smartdatamodels.org/dataModel.Agrifood/soilTemperature",
    "insolation": "https://smartdatamodels.org/dataModel.Weather/solarRadiation",
    "soilTempDepth0_05": "https://smartdatamodels.org/dataModel.Agrifood/soilTemperature",
    "precipitation": "https://smartdatamodels.org/dataModel.Weather/precipitation",
    "airTemperature": "http://purl.oclc.org/NET/ssnx/qu/dim#Temperature",
    "soilTemp0": "https://smartdatamodels.org/dataModel.Agrifood/soilTemperature",
    "relativeHumidity": "https://smartdatamodels.org/dataModel.Weather/relativeHumidity",
    "soilMoistDepth0_2": "https://smartdatamodels.org/dataModel.Agrifood/soilMoistureEc",
    "soilMoistDepth0_1": "https://smartdatamodels.org/dataModel.Agrifood/soilMoistureEc",
    "soilMoistDepth0_4": "https://smartdatamodels.org/dataModel.Agrifood/soilMoistureEc",
    "links": "aim:links",
    "windDirection": "https://smartdatamodels.org/dataModel.Weather/windDirection",
    "soilMoistDepth0_3": "https://smartdatamodels.org/dataModel.Agrifood/soilMoistureEc",
    "windSpeed": "https://smartdatamodels.org/dataModel.Weather/windSpeed",
    "dewPointTemperature": "https://smartdatamodels.org/dataModel.Weather/dewPoint",
    "stationId": "https://saref.etsi.org/saref4agri/WeatherStation"
  },
  "measurementDate": "2025-02-06T14:00:00Z",
  "stationId": "WODR406",
  "airTemperature": 5.2,
  "relativeHumidity": 85,
  "windSpeed": 4.8,
  "windDirection": 23,
  "airPressure": 1019.31,
  "precipitation": 0,
  "dewPointTemperature": 3.3,
  "links": []
}
```

Figure 34: Normalized weather data record from eDWIN API in JSON-LD AIM model.

eDWIN pests' data

Within the eDWIN platform, farmers and advisors collaborate to improve farming procedures. It is important to both predict, using numerical models, appearance chance of diseases and pests on specific fields and types of plants, as well as have a tool to enter real occurrences of agrophage species. The pest data dataset includes detailed reports of all observed diseases and pests, either by farmers, advisors or other personnel. Dataset containing such information could be very valuable for plant protection products producers, small companies providing spraying services as

well as government bodies monitoring condition of farming as well as usage of plant protection products.

To generate this dataset, the data harmonisation pipelines that are part of "Data Harmonisation" module of DATAMITE toolset have been used. This required creation of a specific pipeline, including a mapping specification that aligns source data to the target model (AIM). Fragment of the result of the data pipeline on dataset can be seen on Figure 35.

```
{ "@context": {
  "addressLocality": { "@id": "https://schema.org/addressLocality" },
  "numericValue": { "@id": "http://qudt.org/schema/qudt/numericValue" },
  "bbchStageId": { "@id": "https://w3id.org/aim/ext/phenomenonReporting/bbchStageId" },
  "hasMember": { "@id": "http://www.w3.org/ns/sosa/hasMember", "@type": "@id" },
  "intervention": { "@id": "https://w3id.org/aim/ext/phenomenonReporting/intervention" },
  "occurrenceSeverity": { "@id": "https://w3id.org/aim/ext/phenomenonReporting/occurrenceSeverity" },
  "bbchStageName": { "@id": "https://w3id.org/aim/ext/phenomenonReporting/bbchStageName" },
  "phenomenonTime": { "@id": "http://www.w3.org/ns/sosa/phenomenonTime", "@type": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#dateTime" },
  "observedProperty": { "@id": "http://www.w3.org/ns/sosa/observedProperty", "@type": "@id" },
  "notes": { "@id": "http://foodie-cloud.com/model/foodie#notes" },
  "period": { "@id": "http://foodie-cloud.com/model/foodie#period", "@type": "@id" },
  "lat": { "@id": "http://www.w3.org/2003/01/geo/wgs84_pos#lat" },
  "madeBySensor": { "@id": "http://www.w3.org/ns/sosa/madeBySensor", "@type": "@id" },
  "long": { "@id": "http://www.w3.org/2003/01/geo/wgs84_pos#long" },
  "unit": { "@id": "http://qudt.org/schema/qudt/unit", "@type": "@id" },
  "pestDevelopmentName": { "@id": "https://w3id.org/aim/ext/phenomenonReporting/pestDevelopmentName" },
  "hasResult": { "@id": "http://www.w3.org/ns/sosa/hasResult", "@type": "@id" },
  "distanceFromPoint": { "@id": "https://w3id.org/aim/ext/phenomenonReporting/distanceFromPoint" },
  "label": { "@id": "http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#label" },
  "identifier": { "@id": "http://purl.org/dc/terms/identifier" },
  "hasFeatureOfInterest": { "@id": "http://www.w3.org/ns/sosa/hasFeatureOfInterest", "@type": "@id" },
  "name": { "@id": "https://smartdatamodels.org/name" },
  "resultTime": { "@id": "http://www.w3.org/ns/sosa/resultTime", "@type": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#dateTime" },
  "bbchStageCode": { "@id": "https://w3id.org/aim/ext/phenomenonReporting/bbchStageCode" },
  "hasUltimateFeatureOfInterest": { "@id": "http://www.w3.org/ns/sosa/hasUltimateFeatureOfInterest", "@type": "@id" },
  "developmentStage": { "@id": "https://w3id.org/aim/ext/phenomenonReporting/developmentStage" },
  "dateRange": { "@id": "https://smartdatamodels.org/dataModel.Agrifood/dateRange" } },
  "@graph": [
    { "@id": "http://aims.fao.org/aos/agrovoc/c_5962",
      "@type": "http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#Concept",
      "identifier": { "@value": "c_5962", "@type": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string" } },
    { "@id": "http://aims.fao.org/aos/agrovoc/c_3855",
      "@type": "http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#Concept",
      "identifier": { "@value": "c_3855", "@type": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string" } },
    { "@id": "https://w3id.org/datamite/pilot/pl/pestdiseases/collection/2515",
      "@type": "http://www.w3.org/ns/sosa/ObservationCollection",
      "label": { "@value": "Observation Collection 2515", "@type": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string" },
      "identifier": { "@value": "2515", "@type": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string" },
      "hasFeatureOfInterest": "https://w3id.org/datamite/pilot/pl/pestdiseases/collection/foi/2515",
      "hasMember": [ "https://w3id.org/datamite/pilot/pl/pestdiseases/observation/disease/2024-06-20T20:56:29.410Z",
        "https://w3id.org/datamite/pilot/pl/pestdiseases/observation/disease/2024-06-20T20:56:29.660Z" ],
      "madeBySensor": "https://w3id.org/datamite/pilot/pl/pestdiseases/sensor/1",
      "period": "https://w3id.org/datamite/pilot/pl/pestdiseases/collection/period/2515" },
    { "@id": "https://w3id.org/datamite/pilot/pl/pestdiseases/collection/3359",
      "@type": "http://www.w3.org/ns/sosa/ObservationCollection",
      "label": { "@value": "Observation Collection 3359", "@type": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string" },
      "identifier": { "@value": "3359", "@type": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string" },
      "hasFeatureOfInterest": "https://w3id.org/datamite/pilot/pl/pestdiseases/collection/foi/3359",
      "hasMember": [ "https://w3id.org/datamite/pilot/pl/pestdiseases/observation/pest/2024-07-03T11:49:27.608Z",
        "https://w3id.org/datamite/pilot/pl/pestdiseases/observation/pest/2024-07-03T11:49:52.453Z" ],
      "madeBySensor": "https://w3id.org/datamite/pilot/pl/pestdiseases/sensor/1",
      "period": "https://w3id.org/datamite/pilot/pl/pestdiseases/collection/period/3359" },
```

Figure 35: Fragment of eDWIN Pests dataset normalized by data pipeline process.

AGREGO production data

Final dataset is obtained from another platform, AGREGO. It includes anonymised detailed information about production from fields of the users. It includes start and end dates, crop type, yield and area values as well as economic data of average estimated price and production.

For this dataset, similar to pest data, a data pipeline has been created by utilising tools of “Data Harmonisation” module of DATAMITE. The fragment of the normalized result of the data pipeline is presented in Figure 36.

```
{ "@context": {
  "endedAt": { "@id": "https://smartdatamodels.org/dataModel.Agrifood/endedAt", "@type": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#dateTime" },
  "numericValue": { "@id": "http://qudt.org/schema/qudt/numericValue" },
  "hasByProduct": { "@id": "https://w3id.org/aim/ext/cropProduction/hasByProduct" },
  "secondaryCrop": { "@id": "https://w3id.org/aim/ext/cropProduction/secondaryCrop", "@type": "@id" },
  "isCompleted": { "@id": "https://w3id.org/aim/ext/cropProduction/isCompleted" },
  "price": { "@id": "http://foodie-cloud.com/model/foodie#price" },
  "estimatedAvgProduction": { "@id": "https://w3id.org/aim/ext/cropProduction/estimatedAvgProduction" },
  "productionAmount": { "@id": "http://foodie-cloud.com/model/foodie#productionAmount", "@type": "@id" },
  "estimatedAvgPrice": { "@id": "https://w3id.org/aim/ext/cropProduction/estimatedAvgPrice" },
  "documentNumber": { "@id": "https://w3id.org/aim/ext/cropProduction/documentNumber" },
  "unit": { "@id": "http://qudt.org/schema/qudt/unit", "@type": "@id" },
  "label": { "@id": "http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#label" },
  "name": { "@id": "https://smartdatamodels.org/name" },
  "productionDate": { "@id": "http://foodie-cloud.com/model/foodie#productionDate", "@type": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#dateTime" },
  "startedAt": { "@id": "https://smartdatamodels.org/dataModel.Agrifood/startedAt", "@type": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#dateTime" } },
  "@graph": [
    { "@id": "https://w3id.org/datamite/pilot/pl/production/0",
      "@type": "https://smartdatamodels.org/dataModel.Agrifood/AgriCrop",
      "label": { "@value": "Crop production of pszenica jara on 2014-07-31T00:00:00", "@type": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string" },
      "price": { "@value": "71", "@type": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string" },
      "productionAmount": "https://w3id.org/datamite/pilot/pl/production/0/amount",
      "productionDate": { "@value": "2014-07-31T00:00:00", "@type": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#dateTime" },
      "endedAt": { "@value": "2014-08-31T00:00:00", "@type": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#dateTime" },
      "startedAt": { "@value": "2014-04-01T00:00:00", "@type": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#dateTime" },
      "name": { "@value": "pszenica jara", "@type": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string" },
      "documentNumber": { "@value": "null", "@type": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string" },
      "estimatedAvgPrice": 700,
      "estimatedAvgProduction": 5,
      "hasByProduct": { "@value": "false", "@type": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string" },
      "isCompleted": { "@value": "true", "@type": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string" },
      "secondaryCrop": "https://w3id.org/datamite/pilot/pl/production/0/secondary",
      { "@id": "https://w3id.org/datamite/pilot/pl/production/0/amount",
        "@type": "http://qudt.org/schema/qudt/QuantityValue",
        "label": { "@value": "120.374 tonnes", "@type": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string" },
        "numericValue": 120.374,
        "unit": "http://qudt.org/vocab/unit/TONNE" },
      { "@id": "https://w3id.org/datamite/pilot/pl/production/0/secondary",
        "@type": "https://smartdatamodels.org/dataModel.Agrifood/AgriCrop",
        "label": { "@value": "Secondary crop production of null on 2014-07-31T00:00:00", "@type": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string" },
        "price": { "@value": "null", "@type": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string" },
        "productionAmount": "https://w3id.org/datamite/pilot/pl/production/0/secondary/amount",
        "productionDate": { "@value": "null", "@type": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#dateTime" },
        "name": { "@value": "null", "@type": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string" },
        "estimatedAvgPrice": { "@value": "null", "@type": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#decimal" },
        "estimatedAvgProduction": { "@value": "null", "@type": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#decimal" },
        "isCompleted": { "@value": "null", "@type": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string" } }
    ]
  }
```

Figure 36: Fragment of AGREGO production data normalized by data pipeline process.

Onboarding process for data spaces

Starting from the Code Camp session during a plenary meeting in Poznań an onboarding process has been initiated for PSNC to obtain Gaia-X compliant identity. For this "IDSA & Gaia-X connectors & components" of Data Sharing Module has been used, which facilitates and

automates communication between the data provider and Gaia-X Digital Clearing House. The component has been deployed in the Virtual Machine hosted internally on PSNC's Cloud.

After configuring the component, including obtaining and specifying TERENA domain x509 certificate, a set of JSON descriptions for the onboarding process for the Pilot 5 have been prepared. Those were used in API requests to IDSA & Gaia-X component to complete all the steps required for onboarding. As the result of this process a set of JSON description files were created and served by the IDSA & Gaia-X component of DATAMITE. These descriptions will be reused later during Pontus-X integration and configuration, described below.

Deployment and initial evaluation of DATAMITE platform

As part of test scenario 3 a DATAMITE platform has been deployed on PSNC'S Cloud (Virtual Machine running Ubuntu Server 22.04 LTS Cloud Image, 8 VCPUs, 32GB RAM). During initial installation (during hands-on session at Aachen's Code Camp) we had issues with the Atlas DB component, which has been reported to the platform developer team. Reinstallation with updated version of the platform in January 2025 resulted in successful deployment and start of the assessment of the platform.

The screenshot displays the DATAMITE platform's file upload interface. At the top, there are three tabs: 'Bulk' (selected), 'Streaming', and 'Database Connection'. Below the tabs, the 'File name' field contains 'PME22.csv'. The 'File type' dropdown menu is set to 'csv'. The 'Field Delimiter' and 'Decimal Delimiter' fields are both set to a comma character. In the 'Import the file' section, a file named 'PME22.csv' is shown with a circular arrow icon, indicating it is being uploaded. A 'Create' button is located in the bottom right corner of the interface.

Figure 37: Uploading weather data artefact onto DATAMITE platform.

Examples from Pilot 5 datasets have been uploaded on the platform. Process for one of the artefacts, weather data in a CSV format, can be seen on the Figure 37. Two domains pertaining to the datasets have been created, along with relevant terms dictionary (fragment of which can be seen on the Figure 38). Pilot 5 collaborates with developers of various DATAMITE components, like e.g. Data Product Composition and User Defined Rules Generator, providing necessary requirements and examples to test the components. During first iteration those components have not yet been directly deployed nor tested on Pilot 5 infrastructure yet, but they will be utilised in the second iteration.

Figure 38: Terms glossary for Weather domain defined in the portal.

Polish Agricultural Data Space (Pontus-X) deployment and configuration

One of the main objectives of Pilot 5 is to create a Polish Agricultural Data Space where providers could safely and securely share and trade data products from the agrifood domain. The decision has been made to use Pontus-X, which is a decentralized digital ecosystem that aims to enable secure, compliant, and innovative data sharing, AI services and monetisation across Europe. It is empowered by Gaia-X Trust & Compliance network, and Pontus-X onboarding process is much simplified for already compliant Gaia-X identities. Thanks to previous onboarding process with DATAMITE IDSA & Gaia-X component this means just reusing participant description JSONs stored by the component.

The Pontus-X project consists of two main elements:

- Portal
- Provider

Both components are deployed on PSNC premises – running on Open Shift PaaS Cloud.

All Docker images are stored in PSNC internal registry, with configurations for this specific deployment (both portal and ocean protocol provider) also stored in an internal GitLab code

repository to store and document incremental changes in the configuration. These repositories are modified versions of [deltaDAO/mvg-portal](https://github.com/deltaDAO/mvg-portal)⁴ and [arsys-internet/oceanprotocol-provider](https://github.com/arsys-internet/oceanprotocol-provider)⁵. Full configuration and deployment can be done automatically through the GitLab CI/CD pipeline.

The portal consists of two elements:

- Nginx, which serves the Gaia-X related configuration files obtained during onboarding process of the Pilot 5 in Gaia-X from IDSA & Gaia-X component
- mvg-marketplace, which serves a website that allows users to view and post datasets. it can be accessed via URL: <https://dataspaces.psnr.pl>

Changes mainly consist of configuration chains config, networks metadata, creating deployment for PaaS and major frontend tweaks. All changes can be inspected by comparing the `dcw1` branch with `main`, which is a fork from the original repo.

New versions should be updated by building a new image and then using Helm Chart. e.g.:

```
docker build . -t registry.apps.dcw1.paas.psnr.pl/dataspace-marketplace/mvg-portal:0.16
```

```
cd dcw1_deployment
```

```
helm upgrade mvg-portal ./mvg-portal
```

Provider is the underlying component that allows the publication of datasets. It consists of:

- provider
- operator-engine
- operator-service
- ipfs
- postgres
- redis

It does not provide any GUI, only an API. It can be used within Portal when creating new datasets.

It can be accessed via URL: <https://provider-marketplace.apps.dcw1.paas.psnr.pl>

Full configuration is also stored in the internal GitLab project.

Changes are only made to the infrastructure configuration. No changes to application images.

⁴ <https://github.com/deltaDAO/mvg-portal/tree/main>

⁵ <https://github.com/arsys-internet/oceanprotocol-provider?tab=readme-ov-file>

Values can be adjusted using `dcw1_vales.yaml`. New versions should be uploaded using helm e.g.

```
helm upgrade --namespace dataspace-marketplace helm-provider ./charts/oceanprotocol-provider -f ./dcw1_vales.yaml
```

Asset publishing on Pontus-X

Publishing on Pontus-X platform through DATAMITE platform will require a dedicated Pontus-X broker & plugin. Pilot 5 prepared a stand-alone service that allows publishing of the data assets on Pontus-X platform. Metadata required to integrate DATAMITE platform with Pontus-X publishing, as well as parts of the service implementation, will be reused in creating of the Pontus-X broker for the Data Sharing Module. Details about the service implementation can be found below.

To publish datasets on Pontus-X we were using Nautilus library. Nautilus is a TypeScript library that enables you to explore the Data Economy. Built on top of `ocean.js`, it offers feature-complete, automated interactions with any Ocean Protocol ecosystem. Nautilus serves as a participant agent for programmatic interaction and integration within the Pontus-X ecosystem, enabling users to publish, buy, and consume service offerings efficiently.

For configuration of wallet and data product we specify following parameters:

```
const networkConfig = NETWORK_CONFIGS[selectedNetwork]
const pricingConfig = PRICING_CONFIGS[selectedNetwork]
```

Where `selectedNetwork` is a blockchain network to interact with.

```
export const NETWORK_CONFIGS: {
  [key in Network]: NetworkConfig
} = {
  [Network.GENX]: {
    chainId: 100,
    network: 'genx',
    metadataCacheUri: 'https://aquarius510.v4.delta-dao.com',
    nodeUri: 'https://rpc.genx.minimal-gaia-x.eu',
    providerUri: 'https://provider-marketplace.apps.dcw1.paas.psnc.pl',
    subgraphUri: 'https://subgraph.v4.genx.minimal-gaia-x.eu',
    oceanTokenAddress: '0x0995527d3473b3a98c471f1ed8787acd77fbf009',
    oceanTokenSymbol: 'OCEAN',
    fixedRateExchangeAddress: '0xAD8E7d2aFf5F5ae7c2645a52110851914eE6664b',
    dispenserAddress: '0x94cb8FC8719Ed09bE3D9c696d2037EA95ef68d3e',
    nftFactoryAddress: '0x6cb85858183B82154921f68b434299EC4281da53',
    providerAddress: '0x68C24FA5b2319C81b34f248d1f928601D2E5246B'
  },
},
```

Figure 39: Network configuration in Nautilus

```
export const PRICING_CONFIGS: PricingConfig = {
  [Network.GENX]: {
    FREE: {
      type: 'free'
    },
    FIXED_OCEAN: {
      type: 'fixed',
      freCreationParams: {
        fixedRateAddress: '0xAD8E7d2aFf5F5ae7c2645a52110851914eE6664b',
        baseTokenAddress: '0x0995527d3473b3a98c471f1ed8787acd77fbf009',
        baseTokenDecimals: 18,
        datatokenDecimals: 18,
        fixedRate: '1',
        marketFee: '0',
        marketFeeCollector: '0x0000000000000000000000000000000000000000'
      }
    }
  }
},
```

Figure 40: Pricing configuration in Nautilus.

Configuration of wallet can be done by specifying a private key uniquely identifying the wallet owner as well as provider – a service that enables wallet to communicate with a blockchain network.

```
const wallet : Wallet = new Wallet(privateKey, provider)
```

After the configuration of wallet and target network within Pontus-X/Gaia-X ecosystem we can progress towards publishing our assets. First, we need to specify how provider can access our data set by providing *urlFile* object.

```
const urlFile: UrlFile = {  
  type: 'url',  
  url: datasetUrl,  
  method: 'GET'  
}
```

Next, we create a service on top of our dataset:

```
const service : NautilusService<ServiceTypes, FileTypes> = serviceBuilder  
  .setServiceEndpoint(networkConfig.providerUri)  
  .setTimeout(60)  
  .addFile(urlFile)  
  .setPricing(pricingConfig.FREE)  
  .setDatatokenNameAndSymbol( dtName: 'My Datatoken Name', dtSymbol: 'SYMBOL')  
  .build()
```

where we specify following parameters:

- timeout: how long the service can be used after consumption is initiated
- pricing: your price for accessing this dataset. The data token for this dataset will be worth the entered amount of the tokens.
- providerUri: URL of the data provider
- datatokenNameAndSymbol: A data token is a type of token that represents access rights to a specific dataset or service. This parameter is used to set the name and symbol of this token.

Final step is to create an asset utilizing the service object we just created:

```
const asset : NautilusAsset = assetBuilder
  .setType('dataset')
  .setName("name")
  .setDescription("description")
  .setAuthor('author')
  .addTags( tags: ['tag'])
  .setLicense('license')
  .addService(service)
  .setOwner(owner)
  .build()
```

The created asset object can then be published by issuing

```
const result = await nautilus.publish(asset)
```

```
console.log(result)
```

4.5.3. Training Materials planned

Pilot 5 plans to provide the following training materials:

- Course on 'Data Harmonisation'
In collaboration with task T2.3, a series of short videos will be prepared about data harmonisation using DATAMITE tools and, for example, data sets provided by Pilot 5.
- Data provider integration with Pontus-X
A series of short videos representing data provider integration with Pontus-X, consisting of the configuration of wallet and funds, asset publishing via a web portal and asset publishing via API.

4.5.4. Test Campaign

Progress of the pilot integration with DATAMITE will be showcased in two iterations, aligned with the DATAMITE schedule, presented in the tables Table 19 and Table 20 below.

Iteration Phase 1	
Description	The first iteration focuses on preparing and deploying all necessary components to integrate Pilot 5 data sets with DATAMITE components and platform. This involves creating and deploying necessary internal services responsible for extracting internal data sets from Pilot 5 subsystems as well as data pipelines, responsible for harmonisation and transformation of data sets. During this iteration, the DATAMITE platform, as well as Pontus-X, will be deployed and tested. The onboarding process for Gaia-X compliance will be performed for Pilot 5.
Scenarios	Test scenarios 1-4
Timeline	M23-M26

Table 19: First iteration for Pilot 5

Iteration Phase 2	
Description	In the second phase, deployed components will be used to share Pilot 5 datasets – first directly on Pontus-X data space as assets for testing purposes, then within the DATAMITE platform as data products. Data products will be enhanced by utilizing various DATAMITE components like Data Quality and Governance. Finally, data products will be published on Pontus-X and in other data spaces through the DATAMITE platform. Related Pilot 5 applications will switch some of their services to use shared datasets, exposing them to their users.
Scenarios	Test scenarios 5-7
Timeline	M27-M32

Table 20: Second iteration for Pilot 5

4.5.5. Feedback for improving design

During Pilot 5 trials and test scenarios following feedback has been gathered:

DATAMITE Platform deployment

The first deployment of the platform on Pilot 5 infrastructure (PSNC's cloud infrastructure) was done during the Code Camp session during the Aachen plenary meeting. Thanks to the hands-

on nature of the session, all small issues during the configuration and start-up process have been solved. In this initial deployment, one of the components did not start properly, and data products could not be successfully created from the DATAMITE portal. In the coming weeks, after reinstalling the new version of the platform, everything started working properly.

User Defined Rules Generation improvements

The first iteration of the UDRG component required some further development to satisfy needs of the Pilot 5. During a couple of dedicated meetings, including a meeting at the Code Camp session during the Aachen plenary meeting, we presented our requirements and needs from the pilot's point of view. Suggestions have been taken into consideration for improvements in the UDRG component of DATAMITE platform.

4.5.6. Performance and usability of the DATAMITE framework

Expected Improvements Integration with the DATAMITE framework is expected to have a big impact on several applications and data producers within the pilot, including:

- Promote interoperability by allowing management of different ontologies and vocabularies.
- Ensure that data meets sufficient quality criteria to be shared with third parties, improving the accuracy and reliability of the shared data.
- Ensure marketability (part of data, e.g., energy consumption that is exposed into the DATACELLAR marketplace).
- Define access and authorization policies.

With regards to KPIs full integration of datasets with several modules of DATAMITE is required and is planned in the second iteration of the test campaign, when data products will be able to be published to Polish Agricultural Data Space (Pontus-X). Applications involved in the Pilot will be updated to use datasets shared through the data spaces, exposing them to a wide audience of users.

Progress of the current integration is monitored by the internal KPIs. Three datasets mentioned in the pilot description have been identified and transformed into the required AIM data model. Moreover, Polish Agricultural Data Space has been deployed and established.

KPI	Description	Baseline	Current	Target
KPI1	Datasets under Governance, Quality or Security tools	0	0	3

KPI	Description	Baseline	Current	Target
KPI2	Number of applications using shared datasets	0	0	3
KPI3	Potential users of services/apps/products based on shared datasets	0	0	5000

Table 21: Pilot 5 tentative KPIs

IKPI	Description	Baseline	Current	Target
I1	Number of the dataset being transformed to agreed data models (e.g. AIM)	0	3	6
I2	Number of the datasets shared via the connectors/providers connected	0	0	6
I3	Frontend (marketplace) in place	0	1	1
I4	Dataspace in place	0	1	1
I5	Number of identified datasets	6	9	12
I6	Proposed data models in place	0	0	1

Table 22: Pilot 5 internal KPIs

4.6. Pilot 6 - Connecting MISTRAL to the EU AloD Platform

Weather forecasting requirements and atmospheric model development have resulted in increasing complexity of model physical parameters. As a result, forecasts have become increasingly spatially resolved, placing even greater demands on computing and storage resources required to run model simulations. Being able to guarantee service as complex and critical as weather forecasting, therefore, requires skills and resources with proven reliability, efficiency and track record. The MISTRAL (Meteo Italian Supercomputing Portal) is a platform that facilitates the re-use of weather datasets by the research/business community. The platform aims to process, preserve and provide facilities for the re-use of meteorological datasets at a national level through an Open Data Portal (ODP) and to support the development of downstream services with business potential. The ODP is designed to bring together meteorological data from the observation networks and the civil defence radar network in a central digital repository. It provides historical, real-time analysis, forecasts and probabilistic products such as flash flood

rainfall forecasts. An array of MISTRAL services is provided based on weather observations and numerical model simulations.

Weather forecasts and observations have significant business potential across a range of industries. In agriculture, it supports precision farming and risk management, while in energy it optimises renewable energy production and demand forecasting, to name just a few utilities. Tourism, health and wellness benefit from weather data for planning and risk mitigation. The availability of weather data via APIs or SaaS creates a space for specialised, localised and data-driven solutions. Currently, the stakeholders use the Mistral services and data. In the context of DATAMITE, the pilot aims to disseminate the available data to European portals, particularly AI on Demand (AIoD), a community-driven platform that facilitates knowledge sharing, research experimentation, and development of advanced solutions and technologies related to Artificial Intelligence. This would help to make our data available to a wider audience and to explore possible business opportunities and collaborations.

4.6.1. Test Scenarios

The pilot has two principal test scenarios in the context of DATAMITE. The first one corresponds to the dissemination of Mistral data to European portals, and the second relates to the application of a quality evaluator on Mistral data. What follows are conceived workflows for the test scenarios.

4.6.1.1. Scenario 1: Data dissemination workflow

This first scenario involves distributing Mistral data to the European portal following a generic workflow, as illustrated here. Meteohub is the main interface to MISTRAL, acting as an ODP hosting both data sets and pre-built weather forecast services. Metadata from the Meteohub is ingested into the DATAMITE, either by directly uploading the JSON file or automatically retrieving it from a URL. Both the data ingestion and sharing modules of DATAMITE serve as key components for this step to create the datasets. This is followed by the creation of data products with user-defined features to be disseminated. The data product is then pushed to the AIoD platform via a connector developed specifically for this purpose. DATAMITE also envisages facilitating the dissemination of MISTRAL data products to other European portals through ad hoc connectors that can be used as plug-ins to the data-sharing module, the main advantage being the use of a single framework without the need to restructure or recreate front-end tools for upstream data ingestion and product creation.

Figure 41: Data dissemination through DATAMITE

MISTRAL, in its current implementation, inherently hosts an open data catalogue that is pushed to data.gov.it, which in turn is exposed to the European Data Portal. A specific connector will be developed to partially automate this pipeline using the existing DATAMITE tools. The idea is to push the available data products to the Open Data Catalogue using the CKAN API according to the dcat-ap.it schema, and the rest of the pipeline will be maintained as it currently functions.

4.6.1.2. Scenario 2: Data Quality control workflow

The MISTRAL data arrives from diverse ground stations of weather observation centres.

Figure 42: Data quality control with DATAMITE

The pilot has six requirements for integration with different DATAMITE modules. Firstly, the MISTRAL platform receives input in different formats (CSV, JSON and BUFR), all of which are ingested and harmonised. The resulting output is stored in the MISTRAL-Meteohub data lake.

From data gathered here, the data quality module can be used to perform quality checks on the input data. These datasets, currently, are not subject to any quality control checks within the Mistral implementation, and in the context of the DATAMITE, the current pilot provides a well-suited use case to take advantage of the data discovery and quality control components. The technical discussions with stakeholders have led to the conception of three possible scenarios for data exchange between Mistral and the data discovery component, as shown in the Figure 42. The first option includes the possibility to push the data directly to the data discovery tool. The second method involves the possibility of pulling the data directly from the MISTRAL data lake. The last method is to retrieve the data using SQL queries. The best mode will be selected based on a trial of one or all the scenarios with test bed data. Once the data has been collected, it can be passed to the quality evaluator, which can then extract some built-in KPIs in DATAMITE based on user-defined rules.

4.6.2. Solution implementation

The Pilot 6 implementation consists of two parts. One is the implementation of the MISTRAL platform, and the other is the DATAMITE on-site deployment. As MISTRAL data is not only disseminated but also quality controlled by DATAMITE, the implementation details of both segments are explained below.

Currently, MISTRAL consists of the following solution components

- Ingestor Component: This component collects data from different data providers, harmonises them and stores the harmonised data in the dataset repository. The data to be ingested by the ingestor component are observational data, both coming from ground stations and from radar. The .jsonline, .csv, .bufr, .xml and .geoTIFF data formats are currently supported for input data. The ingestor component has support for the following communication protocols: HTTP, FTP and AMQP
- Dataset repository: based on DBAll-E software for fast access to recent observations and Arkimet software for forecast and observations archive management. BUFR for observed data and GRIB for forecast data are the data formats supported by the dataset repository. Data collected in the repository comes from the ingestor component or, in the case of forecast data, is archived directly into the Arkimet database from the HPC storage systems where the data is generated. Meteo Hub data extraction services can be used to access the data collected in the dataset repository.

- **Meteo Hub⁶**: This component exposes services that are built on top of data, enabling data extraction and filtering as well as data visualisation. Both a web-based user interface and HTTP REST APIs can be used to access Meteo Hub services.
- **Open Data Catalog⁷**: This is based on CKAN technology and publishes the metadata of the datasets available on the Meteo Hub data portal. The Open Data Catalogue (ODC) is currently harvested from data.gov.it, the Italian Open Data Catalogue, and data.europa.eu, the European ODP.
- **Open Data Portal⁸**: This portal provides access to the Meteo Hub services, the MISTRAL Open Data Catalogue and documentation and tutorials related to the MISTRAL services.

The DATAMITE framework has been deployed on an instance of a virtual machine (VM) at CINECA's in-house cloud facility.

- **Configuration**: The VM instance, running Ubuntu24 noble Numbat version, consists of 16 cores of Intel Cascadelake 8260 CPU, 120GB RAM and 300GB storage.
- **Orchestration**: The DATAMITE framework was deployed using Docker Swarm, consisting of a single node, to efficiently use resources to support the computational needs of the various service components.
- **Data ingestion**: Input datasets for testing pilot scenarios will be ingested into the DATAMITE framework either by uploading a bulk file or fetching directly from the URL that exposes the MISTRAL data.
- **Data product composition**: After ingesting input data from a source (local file/URL), the data product to be disseminated is generated using the Data Product Composition module (as shown in the diagram below). This module is currently not integrated into our local DATAMITE deployment, therefore offsite installation has been utilized.

⁶ The Meteo Hub portal is available at the following URL: <https://meteohub.mistralportal.it>

⁷ The Mistral Open Data Catalog can be found here: <https://www.mistralportal.it/catalog>

⁸ The Open Data Portal is available under the following URL: <https://www.mistralportal.it/>

Metadata		Fields	
Title	Unique Id	Version	Issued
MISTRAL	7e5c7e67-d409-4084-ac62-01c4df	1	23/02/2025
Description	Publisher	Size	Metadata Url
FORECAST DATA	DATAMITE	21004	http://datamite.api.tools.iti.gr/produ
Modified	Aggregation Of	Compliant To	Domain
		EDC	Weather
Keyword	Language	Policy	Relevant to
FORECASE	en		
License	Terms And Conditions	Spatial Coverage	Temporal Coverage
Distribution			
Edit			

Figure 43: Mistral data product composition

- Data quality evaluation: Mistral consists of data sets of varying volumes. A small testbed of real data points is ingested using the framework's front-end service to test the quality evaluator module. This process can be automated at a later stage to test the evaluator on larger datasets.

4.6.3. Training Materials planned

Pilot 6 plans to offer the following training webinars, which will focus on the results of the scenarios after thorough testing and validation.

1. Training presentation on "Data ingestion, data production, creation and dissemination".
This webinar will provide a general introduction to weather forecast data, how data is organised within MISTRAL and how integration and dissemination are achieved using the DATAMITE framework, focusing on the expected impact on increasing new business opportunities.
2. Training presentation on "Data Quality Assessment".

This webinar will provide a general overview of the requirements for quality evaluation and how the use of DATAMITE benefits the introduction of quality metrics for our datasets.

This webinar is particularly aimed at our stakeholders outside the DATAMITE consortium.

4.6.4. Test Campaign

In line with the pilot scenarios explained in Figures 41 and 42, the demonstration and testing of the DATAMITE framework will be carried out in three iterations. The first two are related to the dissemination scenario, while the last one is related to the data quality assessment.

Iteration 1	
Description	This phase will focus on on-site deployment of the full DATAMITE framework and will explore the mechanism of data ingestion, data product creation and dissemination to the AIoD portal. Feedback will be shared with the development team for improvement and bug fixing.
Scenarios	1
Timeline	M23 – M27

Table 23: First iteration for Pilot6

Iteration 2	
Description	This phase is dedicated to the organisation of technical meetings with developers (T2.2) to explore the possibility of using DATAMITE to disseminate data in other European portals, in addition to AIoD and the development of an ad hoc broker.
Scenarios	1
Timeline	M25 – M30

Table 24: Second iteration for Pilot6

Iteration 3	
Description	The second iteration focuses on the exploration of data quality assessment on our datasets. In particular, data quality rules will be defined and applied to evaluate the datasets using the integrated KPIs provided by the DATAMITE framework.

Iteration 3	
Scenarios	2
Timeline	M27 – M30

Table 25: Third iteration for Pilot6

4.6.5. Feedback for improving design

During the iteration phase, focused meetings were organised with the DATAMITE development team to share pilot-specific needs on a variety of topics. These included support on issues related to the installation of the local instance of the DATAMITE framework, specifications related to data upload and product composition, longer discussions with feedback on metrics relevant to the quality assessment of our datasets, and the metadata schema required by the ad hoc broker to distribute the pilot data to the AIoD platform.

4.6.6. Performance and usability of the DATAMITE framework

The use of the DATAMITE framework for the pilot scenarios described above has a multitude of benefits as follows:

- Improve the dissemination of the datasets included in the MISTRAL portal by attracting new international users (KPI4, KPI5, and KPI6).
- Improve the reliability of published data by adding data quality attributes (KPI1 and KPI2)
- Improve monitoring of data access, both to prevent the use of data that does not comply with existing licensing policies and to gather data usage statistics that will be useful for exploring business opportunities (KPI3 and KPI6) appropriate business plan.

Table 26 and Table 27 summarise KPI from the DATAMITE and the Pilot internal perspective. The former highlights the general targets expected to be achieved through the utilisation of different DATAMITE components, while the latter elucidates the inherent targets of the pilot.

KPI	Description	Baseline	Target
KPI1	Data Tools, e.g., Governance, Quality, Sharing	None defined	>3 DATAMITE modules
KPI2	Datasets under Governance, Quality or Security tools	0	>90% data involved in the Pilot

KPI	Description	Baseline	Target
KPI3	Datasets under Security, Sovereignty, privacy components	0	>80% data involved in the Pilot
KPI4	Number of national and international active users	~700	Increase 10%
KPI5	Number of catalogues exposing MISTRAL datasets	3	4
KPI6	Dataset exposing data quality attribute	0	>= 90% of datasets involved in the Pilot

Table 26: Pilot 6 tentative KPIs

IKPI	Description	Baseline	Target
I1	Data dissemination to external portals	1	2
I2	Number of components from DATAMITE be used	0	5
I3	Number of developed connectors compatible with internal system to be deployed	0	2
I4	Licence Agreement chosen or formulated	0	≥ 1
I5	Usage Access Policy chosen or formulated	0	≥ 1
I7	Business plan chosen or defined	0	1
I8	Statistics of dataset usages	0	>= 90% of datasets involved in the Pilot
I9	Number of datasets	37	40

Table 27: Pilot 6 internal KPIs

5. Conclusions

This report has presented the progress of Work Package 5 tasks achieved by month 26 of the DATAMITE project.

With the foundational infrastructure now firmly in place and fully operational, the Continuous Integration and Continuous Delivery (CI/CD) strategy for the DATAMITE framework has been successfully implemented. Specific technologies, pipelines, and procedures are in place - established and functioning. For CI/CD, the existing pipelines will be followed, and the rules will likely be updated based on emerging needs. The final release of the DATAMITE framework will have two approaches: one for deployment on a Docker Swarm cluster and another for Kubernetes deployment. Furthermore, all pilots have launched their initiatives utilising the DATAMITE framework, focusing on thorough integration and comprehensive validation. While each Pilot is ultimately working towards the same overarching goals, their approach will be customized to address unique requirements and progress achieved so far. The activities each Pilot will concentrate on next are described below.

Pilot 1, in the next steps, will continue exploring and evaluating the various modules included in DATAMITE, not only focusing on those related to our pilot, with the aim of extracting ideas that enrich our experience. Additionally, the tests will be extended to the complete set of datasets in the context of DATAMITE. Last but not least, the dissemination work will be continued within the group, integrating educational aspects to raise awareness and encourage the incorporation of new users to DATAMITE, especially in stages following the completion of the project.

Pilot 2, during the second iteration, will continue testing and validating the DATAMITE framework in different business scenarios, providing feedback to the technical partners. The aim is to integrate additional datasets coming from various OTE group subsidiaries and thus create more sophisticated data products. As the data quality modules -and particularly the UDRG- will be incorporated into the pilot's deployment, complex business quality rules will be defined based on the available datasets and use cases. Concerning the dissemination of the project, the plan is to publish the pilot's architecture and execution results in scientific conferences and journals.

Pilot 3 next steps focus on preparing for the demonstration of the 2nd iteration by finalising the deployment of all developed DATAMITE components to facilitate testing of the remaining scenarios. Collaborating closely with the developers, feedback will be provided to resolve potential issues with the components during deployment and operation. Additionally, work will

commence on developing training materials on data spaces to support personnel upskilling. Gaining hands-on experience and expanding the understanding of data spaces within the company will foster further exploration of the opportunities they offer.

Pilot 4, from a short-term perspective, will focus on finalising its 2nd level, ensuring the deployment update of the bundle composed of the components from the data governance and data quality module in order to test the components using the datasets and artefacts located in the Azure Storage Account. From a medium-term perspective, the data products will be drafted and created when the component is deployed in Azure. Finally, the data sharing and data security modules will be incorporated in the pilot in order to test data sharing to energy data spaces and to the open data portal, by finalising the onboarding on dedicated IDS and Gaia-X data spaces and through the deployment of the EDC connector. In parallel, E-REDES will continue working on the DATAMITE Business Exploitation strategy through the evaluation of the applicability of the DATAMITE framework in other use cases and through the development and testing of the framework within the company's departments.

Pilot 5 is going to utilise components of the deployed DATAMITE platform to create data products from its datasets and use the platform to publish and share those data products to Pontus-X and other data spaces, thanks to new data brokers. Data Quality and KPI components will be incorporated into the handling of the datasets. Work will also continue in integrating more datasets with the DATAMITE and incorporating data market connection into Pilot 5 applications.

Pilot 6, in the next steps, will focus on integrating the datasets (both metadata and actual test bed data) onto the DATAMITE framework to create data products to be disseminated to the AIoD platform and testing the Data quality evaluator along with in-built KPI of the framework. Subsequently, demonstration videos will be created which would help to elucidate the test scenarios workflow conceived for the pilot.

Looking ahead, the next phase involves continued development tailored to the specific needs of each identified use case scenario, leveraging the established CI/CD pipeline to ensure rapid iteration and reliable deployment of enhancements.